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Position papers and pilot studies on emerging trends in CLS

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General Introduction

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Computational Literary Studies is an area of research which, like its disciplinary context of the Digital Humanities, has a very high affinity with innovation and experimentation and is usually quick to adopt and adapt recent developments in areas of research like Natural Language Processing and Machine Learning. As a consequence, it is a field that is highly dynamic and it is important to monitor not just well-established best practices, tools and requirements (as we have done in previous work within CLS INFRA, notably in Schöch et al. 2023), but also to investigate, discuss and make visible emerging trends in the field which are likely to influence the field, its practices and needs, in the near future.

Documenting three such emerging trends has been the objective of this part of our work within CLS INFRA. We have done this in several different ways: Using both the survey article format to provide overviews of current trends, as well as pilot studies as well as short papers providing background, context and explanations for these pilot studies.

The focus of these outputs is on the following three emerging trends:

1. The use of a recently-developed paradigm in large language models called SetFit (Sentence Transformers Few-Short Learning), investigated here through a pilot study using the SetFit paradigm for the identification of direct speech in narrative fiction, and its description in a short paper.
2. The use of generative large language models such as ChatGPT for investigations of literary texts, presented here as a survey article.
3. The use of the Linked Open Data paradigm in CLS research, exemplified here through a pilot study using LOD for modeling fictional characters, as well as its accompanying short paper.

While these three topics cannot, of course, cover all current emerging trends and topics in Computational Literary Studies, we do hope that these contributions can call attention to several important aspects of current and future CLS as well as provide impulses for focusing on the issues raised here both in technical infrastructure development and in training programmes supporting CLS research.

References

Christof Schöch, Julia Dudar, Evegnia Fileva, eds. (2023). *Survey of Methods in Computational Literary Studies* (= CLS INFRA D3.2: Series of Five Short Survey Papers on Methodological Issues). With contributions by Joanna Byszuk, Julia Dudar, Evegnia Fileva, Andressa Gomide, Lisanne van Rossum, Christof Schöch, Artjoms Šeļa and Karina van Dalen-Oskam. Version 1.1.0, May 5, 2023. Trier: CLS INFRA. URL: <https://methods.clsinfra.io>, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7892112](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7892112).

Exploring SetFit for Direct Speech Recognition: Experiments with German Fiction

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Introduction

Direct speech recognition plays an important role in analyzing literary texts, particularly in detecting dialogue within a narrative. Extracting direct speech from text is often the first step in further text processing, such as network analysis, character interaction studies, and text summarization. As the proportion of direct speech in texts can also impact other methods of analysis, such as stylometry, or other measures, such as sentence length or lexical complexity, and because this proportion in many cases varies with subgenre, it is important to be able to get a sense of how much direct speech there is in narrative texts. However, identifying direct speech in German fiction can be challenging due to historical and stylistic variations, as well as linguistic factors.

In German novels, especially those from previous centuries, different quotation styles are used. Some texts lack quotation marks entirely, meaning direct speech can only be detected through linguistic features and context. Sentences often contain both direct and indirect speech, further complicating recognition. In some cases, direct speech spans multiple sentences, or even multiple speakers, without additional quotation marks. Additionally, inconsistent punctuation and diverse authorial styles make automated detection even more difficult, requiring sophisticated models to capture nuanced patterns effectively.

Direct speech recognition in German fiction has gained attention within computational literary studies due to its complexity and importance in narrative analysis. One of the foundational works in this area is Annelen Brunner's dissertation, *Automatische Erkennung von Redewiedergabe in literarischen Texten (Automatic Recognition of Speech Representation in Literary Texts)*. Brunner introduced an annotation system to categorize various forms of speech and thought representation and developed methods for their automatic detection, setting a strong theoretical foundation for further research in this field (Brunner 2015).

The Redewiedergabe project, funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) from 2017 to 2020, was a collaboration between the Leibniz Institute for the German Language (IDS) in Mannheim and the University of Würzburg. The project focused on analyzing *speech representation (Redewiedergabe)*, such as direct and indirect speech,

in 19th-century texts. Key contributions included the manual annotation of a corpus of both fictional and nonfictional texts and the development of an automatic annotation system for identifying speech representation (Brunner et al. 2020). The recognizer can automatically detect and annotate direct, free indirect, indirect and reported speech, thought and writing representation. Its implementation is based on deep learning with contextual embeddings, namely FLAIR and BERT. The models were trained and tested on historical German fictional and nonfictional texts as well as on modern German fiction. This system was later used to annotate additional materials, creating valuable resources for advancing the study of speech patterns in historical and literary texts.¹

The article “Redewiedergabe – Schritte zur automatischen Erkennung” by Annelen Brunner presents a quantitative approach to speech, thought, and writing representation and steps towards its automatic detection. It summarizes results of a pilot study, describing the manual annotation of a corpus of short narrative texts and the development of automatic detection methods (Brunner 2019).

In the present pilot study, we describe our experiments with developing a new automatic annotation method for direct speech recognition in German literary texts using **SetFit (Sentence Transformer-Finetuning)**, Tunstall et al. 2022, Spielberg 2025). We'll discuss the annotation process, experimental setup, results, and key challenges encountered during the study.

Text Collection and Annotation

For the following experiments we used German third-person fictional narrative texts from the **European Literary Text Collection (ELTeC)**.² While direct speech detection in first-person narrative has its own challenges, the texts chosen here were particularly challenging because the direct speech was often not marked with explicit punctuation or typographic cues. Additionally, in many cases, the direct speech was spread across multiple sentences.

Annotation Process

- **Unit of Annotation:** For our analysis, we initially selected only novels written in the third person. All novels were automatically split into sentences with SpaCy, using the “de_dep_news_trf” model. Novels were annotated at the sentence

¹ More about the project: <https://www.ids-mannheim.de/lexik/redewiedergabe/>.

² See: <https://www.distant-reading.net/eltec/>.

level. If a sentence contained at least one word of direct speech, it was marked as "direct speech."

- **Data:** The initial dataset contained just **33 manually-annotated sentences**. Through iterative fine-tuning, the pre-annotated dataset was progressively expanded to include first 343 and later 743 sentences. Each pre-annotated sentence was manually reviewed, with corrections made to labels as needed. This process culminated in a fully annotated dataset containing 743 sentences.

Experimental Setup and Results

To evaluate the effectiveness of SetFit for direct speech recognition, we conducted experiments with datasets of different sizes, exploring both small-scale and large-scale training configurations. Below is a detailed description of the experimental setup and the results we obtained.

Training on a Small Dataset

The initial experiments began with a small dataset of **33 annotated sentences**. This dataset served as a foundation for testing the feasibility of SetFit on limited data. With this dataset we trained 6 models, trying out different parameters, such as increasing/decreasing sample size, batch size and the number of epochs. After optimizing these hyperparameters, the best performing models demonstrated promising performance, achieving an accuracy of 85 %. For the training of the model we used the following parameters:

- 15 samples per batch
- Batch size: 8
- Number of epochs: 5
- Accuracy: 85%

We think that these results underscore the potential of SetFit to deliver reasonable performance even with minimal annotated data.

Training with Larger Datasets

As the dataset expanded to **743 annotated sentences**, the scope for robust experimentation increased, allowing for more comprehensive training configurations.

The best performing model on the large dataset was trained with the following parameters:

- Sample size: 40
- Batch size: 8
- Number of epochs: 3
- Accuracy: 89.6%

This marked quite a significant improvement, suggesting that increasing the dataset size benefits model accuracy. Note that for this analysis we didn't use the fine-tuned model, but the original one from the JoBeer.³ We also experimented with different parameters, which resulted in 5 trained models. Here are some insights from the experiments with a large dataset.

Performance Adjustments:

1. **Sample Size:** Increasing the sample size to **50** led to a slight decrease in accuracy to **88.5%**; a sample size below **40**, while preserving all other parameters, led as well to a decrease of the accuracy.
2. **Number of Epochs:** Raising the epochs from 3 to **5** yielded a decrease in accuracy to **88.7%**.

Fine-Tuning vs. Original Models

We also experimented with using a fine-tuned model for further fine-tuning. For the small annotated corpus, this led to an increase in accuracy. With the smaller corpus, fine-tuning of pretrained models showed significant benefits. For example, the model trained with a dataset of 343 sentences on the basis of the best performing model from the initial training (with 33 sentences) led to accuracy gains of around **3 percentage points (88%)**, demonstrating its value when annotated data is limited.

However, as the dataset grew, the gap between fine-tuned models and the original **JoBeer model** narrowed. This trend suggests that fine-tuning provides diminishing returns as the amount of annotated data increases. Here you can see the results for the fine-tuned vs. the original model trained with the same parameters (743 Samples, 40 Sample Size, Batch Size 8, 3 Epochs):

³ <https://router.huggingface.co/JoBeer/german-semantic-base>.

- **Fine-Tuned Model:** Accuracy = **87.9%** (fine-tuned with the model trained with **33 samples**),
- **Original JoBeer Model:** Accuracy = **89.6%**

This shows that the original model slightly outperformed the fine-tuned model under the same conditions.

Challenges and Limitations

Despite achieving reasonable accuracy, some challenges persisted:

- **“Accuracy Ceiling”:**
 - Accuracy plateaued around 89.6%, suggesting inherent limitations in the methodology or dataset, despite the increase in training data, sample size, and epochs.
- **Sentence Segmentation and punctuation issues:**
 - The performance of the SpaCy model for sentence segmentation was very low. Despite clear sentence-ending symbols, some sentences were cut off in the middle without any obvious cause. Sometimes, one or two words without any sentence-ending symbols were treated as separate sentences. In other cases, two or more sentences with clear punctuation were combined into a single sentence.
 - Additionally, the punctuation in the novels was not always clear or consistent. Many instances of direct speech spanned multiple sentences without clear delimiters. Sometimes, parts of direct speech were not marked with quotation symbols.
- **Frequent Errors in Evaluation:**
 - Misclassification of indirect speech as direct speech: because of sentence markers such as dashes or exclamation mark: “Zischend und sprudelnd fliegt sie am Stamm des Baumes hinan und – husch! verschwinden die Vögel.”
 - Failure to recognize direct speech when it is embedded without quotation markers often occurs with long direct speech that extends across multiple sentences.

- Sentences that contain both direct and indirect speech are often classified as indirect: “Es kam ihm Alles darin so bekannt vor, daß er den Arm seines jungen Begleiters drückte und auf der Thürschwelle stehen bleibend mit leiser Stimme zu ihm sagte: »Sieh, Paul, das ist die Heimath Deiner Väter!«”
- Despite the presence of first-person pronouns in sentences, they are often marked as indirect speech: “Sie wissen, ich mußte Deutschland meiner Überzeugungen und einiger zufälliger Schulden wegen verlassen, brachte indessen noch so viel baares Kapital hierher, um für einige Monate mich sorglos in das hiesige Treiben stürzen zu können.”

Many of these challenges can be addressed by improving annotated data and refining training processes.

Insights and Future Directions

Based on the challenges and limitations, we can derive key insights and identify future directions:

1. **Data Quality:** Improving sentence segmentation or training custom segmentation models may address issues arising from SpaCy’s limitations.
2. **Model Enhancements:** Through fine-tuning of the transformer models, it may be possible to capture contextual cues more effectively, especially for subtle stylistic patterns.
3. **Annotation Expansion:** While SetFit demonstrates potential with limited data, expanding the annotated dataset with more sophisticated data and clearer punctuation marks might improve accuracy beyond the current plateau.
4. **Error Analysis:** A detailed analysis of frequent misclassifications can aid in model adjustments or feature engineering to prevent recurrent errors.
5. **Training Adjustment:** Increasing the number of epochs or sample size beyond a certain limit can lead to a decrease in performance. It is important to experiment with different parameters to find the optimal ones.

Conclusion

This study explored the use of SetFit for direct speech recognition in German novels, addressing the unique challenges arising from linguistic complexities, diverse quotation styles, and sentence segmentation issues. Through a two-step fine-tuning process and experimentation with different training parameters, SetFit demonstrated its potential as an effective tool for direct speech recognition, achieving a notable accuracy of 89.6% when using a larger dataset for fine-tuning.

However, the study also revealed several limitations, including an accuracy ceiling, issues with sentence segmentation, and frequent misclassifications due to ambiguous punctuation marks in the text. These challenges underscore the need for further advancements in both data preprocessing – such as improved annotation and segmentation – and model architecture to better capture the nuances of German literary styles. Expanding the training dataset with more data, especially with clear and consistent punctuation marks is likely to help further improve the performance. However, we suppose that a token-based sequence classification might be more appropriate for direct speech recognition.

Despite its challenges, SetFit offers a promising approach for direct speech recognition in computational literary studies, bridging gaps in existing methodologies and paving the way for deeper narrative analysis in literary texts. One of the main advantages of SetFit is that it is easy and fast to adjust for specific NLP tasks and different languages. Additionally, even with limited labeled data, it can achieve good performance.

Data and Code

The best performing model can be found on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14917380>. See also the code and data repository: https://github.com/JuliaDudar/Setfit_for_german.

References

- Brunner, Annelen. 2015. Automatische Erkennung von Redewiedergabe: ein Beitrag zur quantitativen Narratologie. *Narratologia*, Band 47. Berlin: de Gruyter.
- . 2019. 'Redewiedergabe – Schritte zur automatischen Erkennung'. *Zeitschrift Für Germanistische Linguistik* 47 (1): 216–48. <https://doi.org/10.1515/zgl-2019-0007>.

Brunner, Annelen / Tu, Ngoc Duyen Tanja / Weimer, Lukas / Jannidis, Fotis (2020): To BERT or not to BERT – Comparing Contextual Embeddings in a Deep Learning Architecture for the Automatic Recognition of four Types of Speech, Thought and Writing Representation, Proceedings of the 5th Swiss Text Analytics Conference (SwissText) & 16th Conference on Natural Language Processing (KONVENS), Zurich, Switzerland, June 23-25, 2020, <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2624/paper5.pdf>.

Tunstall, Lewis, Nils Reimers, Unso Eun Seo Jo, Luke Bates, Daniel Korat, Moshe Wasserblat, and Oren Pereg. 2022. 'Efficient Few-Shot Learning Without Prompts'. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2209.11055>.

Marina Spielberg: "Literary Metaphor Detection with LLM Fine-Tuning and Few-Shot Learning", Jahreskonferenz des DHd-Verbands 2025, Bielefeld University, 3-7 March 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14943239>.

Using ChatGPT in Computational Literary Studies: Applications, Limitations and Future Directions

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Introduction

Computational Literary Studies (CLS), like many other scientific fields, are undergoing significant changes. This transformation is driven by the rise and widespread adoption of advanced technologies that are reshaping research and scholarly work — artificial intelligence (AI) in general and large language models (LLMs) in particular. One of the most widely known and versatile models is ChatGPT, which promises to enable the automation of tasks that traditionally require significant time and human effort. Among these tasks are text annotation, literary translation, classification, and authorship attribution. In theory, AI can improve the efficiency of literary research by reducing time costs, minimizing subjective human errors, and expanding the capacity for processing large volumes of data.

However, like any tool that aims for universal applicability, ChatGPT requires thorough examination and assessment in specific scholarly contexts. While CLS is a relatively young discipline, it already possesses a well-developed methodological framework. It extensively employs Natural Language Processing (NLP) methods. In earlier applications of NLP in CLS, neural networks were used primarily for tasks such as stylometry, text classification, or authorship attribution using tools like scikit-learn or stylo(). Nowadays, large language models like ChatGPT have become standalone tools that can be applied to various CLS tasks, making them an AI-driven method of analyzing texts with high speed and flexibility.

This raises a crucial question: Can we trust the results produced by ChatGPT? Can it replace traditional CLS methods, or does its use require careful optimization and verification? Despite its rapid advancement, ChatGPT still has several limitations: it is highly sensitive to prompt formulation, struggles with understanding complex contexts, and tends to generate so-called hallucinations — misleading or entirely false information presented as plausible and/or factual. Furthermore, the model has not been thoroughly tested across all possible literary analysis tasks and therefore requires additional adaptation. Its results must undergo validation before determining whether ChatGPT can function as a standalone tool in CLS or should only be used alongside traditional methodologies.

This article contributes to the study of artificial intelligence in literary research by examining the advantages and limitations of ChatGPT and other LLMs based on existing studies. It focuses on the application of ChatGPT in CLS as of December 2024. The primary research questions addressed in this study concern the methodological and technical limitations of ChatGPT in literary analysis. We explore how researchers have adapted ChatGPT for the analysis of literary texts, text generation in the style of literary works, authorship attribution, and literary translation. Additionally, this paper examines methods for optimizing language models to improve their accuracy and reliability for specialized CLS tasks.

As AI applications in literary studies continue to expand, this article aims to systematize existing research and explore possible directions for future development. Although various large language models are used in CLS, we focus on ChatGPT because it is one of the most widespread and accessible models for literary research, offering both free and subscription-based versions. The article provides an overview of current approaches to using ChatGPT in CLS, analyzes its limitations, and discusses strategies for adapting the model to literary research tasks.

Section *Evolution of Generative Pretrained Transformers* reviews the evolution of large language models, from rule-based systems to modern LLMs like ChatGPT. Subsection *Performance of LLMs across NLP Tasks* explores the effectiveness of LLMs in NLP methods, which are an integral part of Digital Humanities (DH) and CLS methodologies. Section *Applications of GPT Models in CLS Tasks* presents case studies of ChatGPT applications in three key areas of CLS: literary analysis, text generation and stylometry, and literary translation. We examine text generation and stylometry together because both topics focus on the ways of analyzing, identifying or mimicking unique authorial styles. This is followed by a discussion of the model's limitations and potential directions for future research on the role of ChatGPT in literary studies. The article concludes with a summary of the findings and an outlook on further research possibilities in this field.

Evolution of Generative Pretrained Transformers

An extensive review of language models and their evolution was presented by Zhao et al. (2023). The emergence of large language models represents a transformational shift in natural language processing, marked by four major developmental stages: statistical language models (SLMs) developed in the 1990s, neural language models (NLMs), pre-trained language models (PLMs), and, starting in 2020, large language models (LLMs). This technology has experienced rapid growth and over the past 30 years has evolved from rule-based systems to complex architectures capable of self-learning

through extensive pre-training. These advances have enabled LLMs to address complex NLP problems without the need for fine-tuning to a specific task (Zhao et al. 2023).

From Rule-Based Systems to Generative Transformers

Artificial Intelligence started to develop in the 1950s, and this is the time when the first NLP systems appeared. The models of that time, up to the 1980s, were mostly based on rules written by human experts. They were mainly used in highly specialized tasks, such as syntactic parsing and information extraction (Kalyan 2024).

However, these systems were unable to perform more complex tasks. Additionally, they were too expensive and labor-intensive to maintain, which drove the transition to models relying on statistical learning methods. This new type of model, called statistical language model, emerged in the 1990s and was able to use probabilistic methods for n-gram-based word predictions. Despite their better performance in information retrieval, these models also had many limitations, related in particular to the estimation of probability (“curse of dimensionality”) (Zhao et al. 2023).

The 2010s brought a major transition that marked a new stage in the development of artificial intelligence — the rise and spread of neural network technology, especially multi-layer perceptron (MLP) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) (Zhao et al. 2023). It became possible to use not only word probabilities but also to automatically create word vectors, also known as word embeddings, using word2vec and GloVe, turning words into numerical vectors that express semantic relationships, in order to make them readable for a machine. The introduction of deep learning-based models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) (Kalchbrenner et al. 2014), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) (Salehinejad et al. 2017), and Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs) (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber 1997) brought significant improvements. However, these architectures faced challenges: MLPs struggled to capture sequence information and semantic relationships; CNNs excelled at extracting local features but failed with long-term dependencies; RNNs handled sequential data better but suffered from the problem of so-called *vanishing gradients*. This problem occurs when important information fades as it moves through the layers of a neural network, making it difficult for the model to learn long-term patterns. LSTM and GRU were developed to solve this issue, however, these model variations led to high computational costs due to sequential processing (Kalyan 2024).

Since the mid-2010s, the concept of pre-trained language models started to develop rapidly. In 2017, the transformer architecture was introduced and since then it has become possible to process large amounts of data more efficiently (Vaswani et al. 2017). Part of a broad class of large language models, generative pre-trained transformers (GPT) are a family of language models introduced to a broader audience by OpenAI, now commonly used by many other developers. Built on the transformer architecture, GPT models utilise predictive language modelling, generating the next word based on previous tokens, to learn rich semantic and syntactic patterns from corpora. The importance of GPT models lies in their ability to perform In-Context Learning (ICL), where a model can infer and solve tasks based on natural language instructions and a few examples (Kalyan 2024).

The era of GPTs as we know them now dates back to 2018. In the article *Improving Language Understanding by Generative Pre-training* by Alec Radford et al. (2018), the researchers introduce a language model called Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT). This model uses a pretrain-then-fine-tune paradigm, that was pre-trained in an unsupervised manner on large corpora, then fine-tuned for specific tasks and was mostly used for NLP tasks. However, because GPT is later adopted to tasks with labeled data, this approach can be seen as semi-supervised learning, where models learn from both unlabeled and labeled data: first it learns general language representations without labels, then it refines them with supervision (Radford et al. 2019). Such models, like BERT (Devlin et al. 2019) or GPT-1 (Radford and Narasimhan 2018), were effective on various benchmarks, when compared to earlier models. While GPT, as a generative model, was mostly used for text generation, BERT, as it does not produce text, proved to be effective for text understanding tasks. RoBERTa (Liu et al. 2019), XLNet (Yang et al. 2020), ALBERT (Lan et al. 2020), DeBERTa (He et al. 2021), GPT-2 (Radford et al. 2019), and BART (Lewis et al. 2019) evolved from these models. The number of parameters increased to 1.5 billion, while the WebText dataset significantly enhanced text generation capabilities of this model.

The release of GPT-3 was widely recognized in the research literature as the emergence of large language models (Brown et al. 2020, Quin et al. 2023). The number of parameters increased significantly to 175 billion, the parameters were scaled, and the in-context learning technology was greatly improved to include few-shot, one-shot and zero-shot learning without fine-tuning (Brown et al. 2020). GPT-3 was used to build models such as PaLM (Chowdhery et al. 2022), Chinchilla (Hoffmann et al. 2022), LLaMa (Touvron et al. 2023), LaMDA (Thoppilan et al. 2022) and many others (Kalyan 2024).

In December 2024, the latest versions available to users are GPT-4o and GPT-4 Turbo, based on the GPT-4 version released in 2023 (OpenAI et al. 2023). This model was the next step forward in the development of large language models. The main difference to previous models is multimodality – that is, the ability to handle text, sound and images. Also, improvements have been made to the ability to generate text, reasoning in dialogue form. Much attention is paid to the security of generated responses, the use of red teaming, a method of handling undesirable and potentially harmful queries, and the technology of reinforcement learning via human feedback (RLHF), which is a training method based on improving model’s outputs using human feedback. Another current issue and area of improvement is the problems with so-called “hallucinations” (Kalyan 2024).

Performance of LLMs across NLP Tasks

Large language models show significant promise in a variety of NLP tasks. Many efforts are being made to advance the zero-shot performance, aiming to improve LLM’s ability to perform analysis without additional data, based only on a simple user query (prompt). This approach often mimics communication with another person, as analysis takes the form of a dialogue. For training language models, especially ChatGPT, reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) is used, which increases the ability of LLMs to process human inputs and natural language effectively (Qin et al. 2023). Tasks such as machine translation, summarization, and dialogue are usually well handled by large language models (Zhao et al. 2023).

However, the performance of language models, including ChatGPT, is still under active development, being the research subject of numerous performance tests for NLP tasks. For example, Chengwei Qin’s work (2023) focuses on the performance of ChatGPT and GPT-3.5 on basic NLP tasks such as question answering, dialog, summarisation, sentiment analysis and several kinds of reasoning. On some tasks, performance is high (e.g. dialogue tasks), but on more specific tasks, such as sequence tagging, the model faces notable challenges (Qin et al. 2023). In addition, the dependence of model performance on languages (it is higher in English) and on specialised domains, where further expertise is often required, are mentioned among limitations of this model.

In semantic tasks such as word clustering and word sense parsing, LLMs achieve comparable performance to smaller models due to contextual learning, although smaller, specialised models often outperform them on domain-specific datasets. For named entity recognition (NER) and part-of-speech (POS) labelling, LLMs struggle with ambiguous categories such as “MISC” (miscellaneous) and “ORG” (organisations) due

to restricted context understanding and insufficient training data (Zhao et al. 2023). For extracting structured information, such as identifying relationships or events, LLMs tend to lag behind specialised methods trained on large datasets, but perform well in zero-shot and few-shot scenarios when using multi-stage approaches (Zhao et al. 2023).

Despite these shortcomings, LLMs are continuously developing and being applied not only to NLP tasks but also to specialised tasks from specific domains, such as literary analysis and working with fictional texts. In the next chapter we will look more closely at the methodology and approaches in applying GPT technology to computational literary studies tasks.

Applications of GPT Models in CLS Tasks

The evolution of GPT models has made them a powerful tool in Computational Literary Studies. Since GPT-2, these models have shown promising applications in text generation, interpretation, and classification. In GPT-3 and its advanced versions, such as GPT-3.5-turbo, and in GPT-4o, researchers have exploited the potential of zero-shot and few-shot learning, allowing the models to solve complex problems with minimal human-provided examples.

In the context of CLS, three main areas of application are identified in the research literature: literary analysis, text generation and stylometry, and literary translation. These studies predominantly use versions from GPT-2 to GPT-4, with GPT-4 showing significant progress in contextual understanding and generative tasks. In addition to the GPTs, other models specially trained for specific tasks such as LLAMA, LLAMA 2 (Touvron et al. 2023), BERT, are also actively used for CLS tasks.

The following sections focus on key areas of CLS applications, starting with section *Literary Analysis*, which addresses tasks such as text interpretation, classification tasks and automatic annotation. The next section is devoted to the topic of ChatGPT's performance in text generation and stylometry tasks. Section *Literary Translation* covers literary translation and how generative transformers can be applied in this domain.

Literary Analysis

ChatGPT makes it possible to perform more detailed analyses of literary texts. In literary studies, this tool is mainly used for text interpretation, narrative analysis tasks, and automatic annotation. This section provides examples of how ChatGPT and other LLMs have been applied to these tasks.

Text Interpretation

Understanding and interpretation of textual information is a key criterion of a language model's effectiveness. Literary texts often pose a challenge for artificial intelligence because they are rich in metaphors, irony, author's style and other forms of linguistic expressiveness, which humans often interpret better than language models. Several interesting studies have been conducted to investigate the ability of ChatGPT to interpret literary texts.

Pagel et al. (2024) aimed to investigate knowledge transfer between literary characters and their family relationships in German drama using zero-shot and few-shot settings. For this purpose they used a corpus consisting of 30 texts taken from DraCor. The corpus was pre-annotated and the annotation included different family relations (parent, child, etc.). Three language models – LLAMA 2, Platyplus (Lee et al. 2024), ChatGPT-4 – were used for the experiment and tested on classification and textual entailment tasks in order to detect and identify specific family relationships in the dialogues. The researchers found that LLAMA 2 outperformed other models in the classification task, whereas ChatGPT-4 achieved better results in the textual entailment task. However, it should be said that both models did not cope at a sufficient level with implicit relationships unless explicitly stated (Pagel et al. 2024).

Also of interest are studies that compare the effectiveness of ChatGPT and human evaluators for identifying themes and analysing complex literary devices that require a deep understanding of the material. For example, Garret and Nevedha (2024) conducted such a study using the example of poetry, namely *The Cost of Love* by Fiona Kezia Winston. Data on human interpretations were collected through a survey of 130 participants. Both survey participants and ChatGPT were asked the same questions about the poem and the topics, ideas, and literary methods used in the poem. ChatGPT's interpretations were compared with human responses and with the poet's own interpretation, who actively participated and contributed to the study. The responses were then analysed on aspects such as the ability to recognise themes, literary elements (metaphors, alliteration, symbolism etc) and understanding of tone and emotion. The authors do not specify which version of ChatGPT was used in this study, but based on the date of the article (January 2024), it can be assumed that this is the current version of GPT-3 or higher (available for the second half of 2023). Despite some difficulties in interpreting specific details, the model generally succeeded in identifying central themes, tone, relationships, key literary devices and the author's intent. The authors conclude that ChatGPT can be used in addition to human analysis for more versatile analysis (Garret and Nevedha 2024).

The improving performance of the latest GPT-4 model, even when compared to human analysis, is confirmed by a paper by Ted Underwood. In his study, the researcher investigated the ability of a language model to predict plot twists in stories and fairytales (Underwood 2024). The experiment included human readers predicting story developments, which were then compared to both ChatGPT's predictions and the actual continuation of the text. The results showed that in the case where the story does not have a unique narrative style, ChatGPT did well and showed correlation with human predictions even at points where readers had difficulty predicting the plot.

Another noteworthy study by Underwood (2023) investigated the language model's ability to detect and analyse the passage of time in fiction. In this study, a corpus of 483 previously annotated literary passages from the 18th century's fiction to the present day was used. The main criterion for selection was the presence of complex time constructions in the works (the concept of "eternity", length of time described, etc.) (Underwood 2023). ChatGPT (GPT-turbo and GPT-4 versions) was asked to label the passages and determine how long the event described in the text lasts. Human participants were also involved in the experiment to manually label the time passages. ChatGPT's results were then compared with human analysis, which served as a benchmark. Manual analysis achieved the highest results, followed by the GPT-4 model (a newer, paid version at that moment) with a slight drop off. The regular version of ChatGPT-Turbo quite strongly underperformed compared to human analysis, but performed better than linear regression and ridge regression (Underwood 2023). Among the advantages of the language model, the author mentions its cost-effectiveness and speed, recommending it for researchers with minimal programming knowledge.

Literary Annotation

Literary text annotation is one of the tasks that could be automated using artificial intelligence, reducing the need for manual work. Automation can greatly simplify, reduce the cost of, and speed up the annotation process. The potential of ChatGPT in this area is currently being actively explored.

One such research is the CLAUSE-ATLAS⁴ project, whose creators are testing the capabilities of ChatGPT-3.5-turbo for automatic annotation of literary texts at the level of clauses. Clauses are understood as units of textual information carrying event, subjective and contextual information (Troiano and Vossen 2024). Thus, three distinct types of clauses — and corresponding classification categories — were identified. The CLAUSE ATLAS corpus includes six works in English from the 19th and 20th centuries,

⁴ <https://huggingface.co/datasets/troianeana/CLAUSE-ATLAS>

including *Alice in Wonderland*, *The Great Gatsby*, and others (Troiano and Vossen 2024). In total, the corpus includes 41,715 clauses annotated both automatically and manually. The language model was used in zero-shot and few-shot mode and tested on three types of prompts (P1, P2, P3), each varying in detail and instructional specificity. Human annotation was conducted for the first chapters of three books (*Alice's Adventures in Wonderland*, *The Adventures of Pinocchio*, *The Great Gatsby*) by three people. As a result, the test showed that nearly half of the manual and automatic classification results matched (49% match). Agreement among human annotators was predictably higher, but not critically so (56%). After further analysis, agreement with ChatGPT reached 76%, demonstrating a strong level of performance. The authors note that one particular prompt among several proved to be the most accurate, and its results were used to further analyse the structure of the texts. Overall, despite difficulties with ambivalent cases or errors in the segmentation process, the authors conclude that annotation using the language model has potential and can be applied in analysing large literary corpora (Troiano and Vossen 2024).

One of the challenges, which is difficult even for human beings, is the issue of narrative perspective. It can be difficult to distinguish between the way in which information is conveyed to the reader, i.e. focalisation. Focalisation is categorized into three types: internal (through character perception), external (through a narrator who exists within the fictional world but does not coincide with any character) and zero (via an all-knowing narrator). The time-consuming yet intriguing task of annotating focalisation and the prospects of using a language model to address it are explored in the study *Says Who? Effective Zero-Shot Annotation of Focalisation* (Hicke et al. 2024). The analysis is based on the corpus of Stephen King, which includes 16 novels published from 1975 to 1999. A special aspect of this experiment is that it involves quite a large number of language models – namely seven, including the popular large-scale language models GPT-3.5, GPT-4, GPT-4o, open-source LLAMA 3 (8B and 70B parameters), and two more lightweight baselines such as DistilBERT and a Naive Bayes classifier with TF-IDF. Three experts were engaged to manually annotate the 96 extracts, after which the results were discussed to agree on the labels.

The study revealed that automatic annotation with GPT-4o achieved the best performance, comparable to human consensus annotation, with an F1-score of approximately 86%. Human annotators faced difficulties in distinguishing between internal and external focalization, particularly when environmental details could be interpreted either from a character's perspective or by an external observer. The GPT-4o model was the most consistent and demonstrated high agreement across

multiple annotation runs with the Krippendorff's α of 0.96, which indicated that the model applies focalization labels in a systematic and repeatable manner. Internal focalization was the easiest to identify, achieving the highest F1-score among the three focalization types. Interestingly, the task was completely impossible for the Naive Bayes model, which assigned the label "internal" to all passages. In general, all models except Naive Bayes performed well on the focalisation task, according to the authors. However, there were still difficulties associated with, for example, the need for a wider context, as the excerpts were relatively short (starting from 50 words) and the corpus was limited to a single author's work (Hicke et al. 2024).

Classification

Two key studies, by Kuzman et al. (2023) and Le Mens et al. (2023), examine ChatGPT's effectiveness in classification tasks. Both studies raise the issue of genre classification and test the effectiveness of language models for these tasks. The authors highlight the relevance of automated annotation methods, as manual annotation is often time-consuming and sometimes challenging even for humans (Kuzman et al. 2023).

Le Mens et al. study the ability of ChatGPT-4 to measure the genre typicality of texts (books and political tweets), i.e. the model's ability to determine whether a text matches the typical features associated with a particular genre category. The test was conducted for two genres, mystery and romance. The test data for both genres consisted of 500 books of the respective genre and 500 books whose label was different from the target genre. The labels and book descriptions were taken from public sources including Goodreads.com, Amazon description and cover-jacket text. The approach of this study was to directly query ChatGPT using a special prompt, whereby ChatGPT should give a score from 0 to 100 and evaluate the typicality of the book. This score was then compared to aggregate typicality measures that were prepared based on several human evaluations and to the BERT model score. As a result, ChatGPT matched human evaluators in genre classification accuracy and effectively assessed how well texts fit genre categories. The authors conclude that ChatGPT's performance was even better than its performance on evaluating tweets and their relevance to political parties (Le Mens et al. 2023).

Kuzman's study focuses on the genre classification of texts from the bilingual English and Slovenian GINCO⁵ corpus, which consists of texts of 24 genres. Among them, literary genres are labelled as prose and lyrical, included in one label and which include Lyrics, poetry, prayers, anecdotes, novels, short stories. The two models ChatGPT 3.5

⁵ <https://www.clarin.si/repository/xmlui/handle/11356/1467>

and X-GENRE were tested on 100 instances from each dataset in English and Slovenian and performance was tested on randomly selected samples. For such a rare category (1% of the training data in the GINCO corpus and 6% in the X-GENRE model data) the model performance was quite low and the results are only relevant for the Slovenian corpus. ChatGPT outperformed the trained X-GENRE model on the English dataset EN-GINCO (Micro F1 = 0.74 vs. 0.67), but lagged behind on the Slovenian GINCO (Micro F1 = 0.75 for English Prompt and 0.68 for Slovenian vs. 0.91 for X-GENRE). Despite the effectiveness of ChatGPT in the experiment, the models had difficulties with the prose/lyrical category due to lack of data. However, the effectiveness and promising performance were emphasised by the authors, as ChatGPT demonstrated the ability to categorise hybrid texts and account for multiple genres, which was rarely seen in trained models.

Limitations of ChatGPT in Literary Analysis

As studies show, the limitations of ChatGPT performance in literary analysis can be related to both technical and linguistic aspects.

Findings from the study on German drama suggest that historical and literary texts pose challenges for language models. For example, ChatGPT struggled with 18th- and 19th-century literary language, particularly when dealing with texts outside its training data. In addition, the study showed strong sensitivity to prompt, so that the slightest changes in input led to changes in the results of the analyses. This suggests that ChatGPT lacks a deep understanding of complex contexts. As a consequence, the test showed difficulties with surface level reasoning and a tendency to identify only those relationships between characters that were explicitly stated in the text. It also has sparse data issues and requires, as the authors advise, the application of fine-tuning methods like PEFT or LoRA (Pagel et al. 2024).

Similar problems were observed in *The Cost of Love* study, where ChatGPT exhibited a limited ability to interpret specific details and concepts (Garret and Nevedha 2024). There are problems with ambivalence, with the interpretation of verbs of perception (“saw”, “heard”), and difficulty in distinguishing between external observation and internal perception (Hicke et al. 2024).

Ted Underwood’s experiments on narrative prediction further emphasized this limitation. While GPT-4 performed well on conventional narratives, it often relied on clichés and common narrative patterns rather than offering innovative or nuanced predictions. This highlights the model’s lack of deep thematic understanding and creative insight, which

are essential in literary contexts. Underwood adds that universities need to build their own models and task-specific APIs with the ability to tune (Underwood 2024). Overall, he notes that large language models still need to be used with caution and have not yet succeeded in completely replacing human analysis.

Prompt dependency, one of the current limitations of language models, is also noted in the Troiano and Vossen's (2024) study. Variation in prompts led to significant changes in results and critical variations in annotations. In Kuzman's work on bilingual categorisation, ChatGPT performed the poorest when dealing with prompts in Slovenian. This reflects persistent issues with non-English prompts, which continue to exhibit lower accuracy even in newer models.

Text Generation and Stylometry

Poetry Generation

The application of ChatGPT and other language models for the automated generation of text in general and poetry in particular is becoming an increasingly popular trend in digital humanities research. A variety of studies show that both older models like GPT-2 (Dai 2021), and newer versions such as GPT-3.5 and GPT-4 (Walsh et al. 2024; Mikołajec 2024) are able to reproduce certain genre and stylistic features of poetic texts, demonstrating both their capabilities and limitations.

Alice Dai (2021) explores in her study GPT-2's ability to reproduce characteristic elements of Emily Dickinson's poems. The model was trained on a corpus of 586 stanzas. Preprocessing included several steps, such as removing markup errors, adding special tokens for line boundaries, and standardizing abbreviations. Experimental results showed that GPT-2 successfully mimicked key stylistic features such as abundant use of dashes, unexpected capitalization and syntactic constructions. Moreover, the model generated rich metaphorical images. For example, the line "Eternity is a hinge" demonstrates the system's ability to form unusual and expressive word associations characteristic of Dickinson's work. At the same time, the model showed a limited capacity for thematic coherence and deep philosophical reflection. Dai emphasizes that more powerful language models and enhanced training data are needed to achieve higher levels of creativity and depth in texts (Dai 2021).

A more recent study, *Does ChatGPT have a poetic style?*, which is particularly relevant to this topic, was conducted by Walsh et al. in 2024. It focuses on the generation of poems of various forms and complexity, including fixed poetic forms such as sonnets, villanelles, sestinas, and limericks. Two versions of ChatGPT, GPT-3.5 and GPT-4, were

provided with three types of queries (prompts): general, figurative and specific. They were asked to generate texts on 24 different poetic forms and 40 themes such as nature, relationships and holidays. For analysis, the model generated 5,760 poems, which were then compared to a corpus of 3,692 human poems from the Poetry Foundation and the Academy of American Poets.

The results showed that GPT-4 significantly outperformed GPT-3.5 in meeting genre requirements, including line length, rhyme scheme, and meter. For example, GPT-4 generated sonnets (14 lines) with correct structure, villanelles (19 lines), and sestinas (39 lines). At the same time, both models showed a tendency to use structural elements such as four-line stanzas, rhyme, and iambic meter, even in forms where this was not required. Lexical analysis revealed frequently occurring words and phrases such as “heart”, “embrace”, “echo”, “whisper”, forming a recognizable stylistic signature of a GPT-generated text, but also indicated limited creative variation. This study demonstrates that ChatGPT can reproduce complex genre forms while remaining faithful to their stylistic requirements, but also reveals a limitation in deep artistic diversity (Walsh et al. 2024).

There is another recent study by Mikołajec (2024) that examines GPT-3.5 and GPT-4’s ability to generate poetic texts. The methodology included advanced prompting, where researchers set detailed queries to guide the model. The queries specified genre requirements, style, and context. For example, participants asked ChatGPT to imagine itself as a poet inspired by Shakespeare or to write a sonnet on the topic of internal conflicts, such as the struggle between reason and feelings. This approach, called “interactive quality control” or “guided generations through detailed prompts”, allowed the model to produce more meaningful and stylistically accurate texts that retained intertextual connections and artistic value. The results showed that GPT-4 coped with the formal requirements of the genre, such as the 14-line sonnet structure, rhyme and meter, significantly better than GPT-3.5. The latter model often struggled with maintaining formal constraints, frequently producing lines with inconsistent length and rhyme scheme. Lexical analyses revealed that the model texts included universal poetic themes such as the motif of light and darkness and the inner conflict between reason and feelings (Mikołajec 2024).

Stylometry

Stylometry is an area of Computational Literary Studies that allows researchers to study authorial style, genre features, and the evolution of literary texts using quantitative methods. ChatGPT and other language models are not only applied to analyse and

simulate authorial styles, but also provide new tools for solving problems such as AI text detection. This section discusses examples of the use of ChatGPT for stylometry, both in CLS tasks and as a part of other methods that can be adapted for literary research.

Stylometry for Literary Style Imitation

Although the use of ChatGPT as an independent tool for stylometry is not well covered in the research literature due to its novelty, we found some noteworthy studies. One such example of using ChatGPT and other language models in CLS tasks is the study *GPT-3 vs. Delta. Applying Stylometry to Large Language Models*, where the ability of GPT-3 to mimic the stylistic features of authors was analysed (Rebora 2023). The study was based on the ELTeC (European Literary Text Collection) corpus, which included the works of 10 English authors. The Cosine Delta method based on the 150 most frequent words (MFW), which is a standard approach in stylometric analysis, was applied for evaluation. The corpus was divided into training and test sets, with the test data consisting of 345 text samples of 5,000 words each.

The style imitation process was based on specially designed prompts, such as “Write a chapter of a novel in the style of Charles Dickens” or “Write a story as if it were written by Jane Austen”. Several variants of GPT-3 were used for generation, including DaVinci, Curie, Babbage, and Ada. The generation “temperature”, i.e. the rate of deviation of the model from typically machine to more creative output, ranged from 0.1 to 0.9, allowing texts of varying degrees of “creativity” to be modelled (Rebora 2023).

The results showed that GPT-3-generated texts were correctly attributed to the target author only 16.8% of the time, indicating the model's limited ability to accurately reproduce stylistic features. Nevertheless, the analysis revealed interesting linguistic trends in the generated texts through which it was possible to recognise texts written by the language model. For example, reduced lexical diversity and repetitive patterns made GPT-3 texts easily identifiable, despite attempts to imitate the style of other authors (Rebora 2023).

Thus, this study suggested that while GPT-3 could replicate some elements of authorial style, it struggled with understanding and conveying complex linguistic constructions. The language model still leaves so-called imprints, characterized by its distinct linguistic patterns, which limits its ability to achieve highly accurate imitation of authorial style. This emphasises the need for further developments to improve the adaptability and accuracy of the models.

Stylometry for Authorship Attribution

Recent studies on stylometry, which traditionally has been used for authorship attribution, are now increasingly integrating large language models (LLMs), including ChatGPT, as a methodological tool. Specific models are often being fine-tuned for attribution tasks. Recent studies demonstrate that LLMs can be particularly effective in analyzing short text segments and tackling complex attribution challenges, often outperforming traditional methods in specific scenarios.

For example, the paper by Hicke and Mimno (2023) presents work with language models for authorship attribution on very short passages. In their work, they test T5, a type of generative language model that has been specifically tuned for authorship attribution tasks. The fine-tuned language models proved to be highly efficient and outperformed other methods (including SVM and Cosine Delta). In addition, they performed well in style quantification. The authors highlight certain weaknesses in language models, arguing that LLMs are more likely to misattribute texts to certain authors if they have a larger-than-average vocabulary and tend to use corpus-standard lexicon. Based on the results of their study, the authors conclude that large-scale LLMs demonstrate impressive accuracy in identifying authors of short text segments (5-450 words), as such texts fit within their processing limits. In contrast, traditional methods like Cosine Delta perform better on longer texts (Hicke and Mimno 2023).

Schmidt et al. (2024) conducted an experiment on author attribution in Latin, a low resource language. The dataset is based on the Patristic Sermon Textual Archive (PaSTA), focusing on Latin homiletic literature from the 3rd to the 7th centuries, involving 22 authors in total. The study evaluates four major LLMs: GPT-4o, Claude, Mistral-Large, and Gemini-1.5. The texts were divided into "work-units" (self-contained acts of preaching), with each unit split into chunks of approximately 250-500 words. These chunks were sampled to create pairs for authorship verification (determining whether two texts were written by the same author) and attribution tasks (identifying the author of a given text from a predefined set). In the author verification task, GPT-4o and Claude outperformed traditional baselines, including LaBerta-based models, in terms of accuracy, particularly in the BASE (simple task description) and LIMITED (Instruction to focus on writing style) prompt settings. In authorship attribution GPT-4o achieved the highest performance when analyzing text fragments of 250 words with 5 candidate authors, though it slightly decreased for longer text (500 words) and a larger number of candidate authors (Schmidt et al. 2024).

How does artificial intelligence respond when faced with the challenge of determining authorship for texts specifically designed to imitate an author's style? Such a question is raised in *Forged-GAN-BERT: Authorship Attribution for LLM-Generated Forged Novels* by Silva et al. (2024). The Forged-GAN-BERT model was selected for testing, and its results were compared to those of BERT, RoBERTa and the Longformer model, which is characterized by its ability to effectively handle long documents using a specialized attention mechanism (Beltagy et al. 2020). Forged-GAN-BERT was the best-performing model. Authorship attribution of AI-generated novels is feasible but challenging. Traditional models struggle when faced with forged texts mimicking an author's style. LLMs like ChatGPT can generate highly convincing forgeries, especially when conditioned on an existing novel. The authors argue that the results are optimistic enough to proceed with an expanded dataset and a more specifically tuned methodology (Silva et al. 2024).

Stylometry for Analyzing Canonical Texts

The analysis of canonical and non-canonical texts using ChatGPT and perplexity, as described in the study by Wu et al. (2024), provides useful methods and insights for CLS tasks. Although the study itself focuses on the perplexity metric, its application to a corpus of over 9,000 novels to study text complexity provides an opportunity to transfer these approaches to literary analysis.

The study found that some canonical works, such as James Joyce's *Finnegans Wake*, exhibit the highest perplexity values among the analyzed texts. This is due to a very uncommon linguistic structure, high lexical diversity, and syntactic complexity, which make them less predictable for both human readers and language models. One reason for high perplexity is the use of a “nominal style”, characterized by a high ratio of nouns and adjectives to verbs. This makes the text denser and less predictable, requiring much cognitive effort from readers and language models to process it (Wu et al. 2024).

These findings have several important implications for CLS:

1. Identifying stylistic features: High perplexity values correlate with linguistic and cognitive complexity of the text, which can be used to quantitatively analyze literary complexity and language uniqueness;
2. Understanding the canon: The study confirms that canonical texts use linguistic techniques such as defamiliarization and foregrounding, requiring the reader to engage in active interpretation with the text. This is particularly important for analysing literary texts, where such techniques form a unique artistic value;

3. Integration with stylometry: Combining perplexity with more traditional stylometric methods such as Type-Token Ratio or lexical diversity metrics can provide a more complete picture of what makes a text canonical or not. In the context of CLS, this opens up the possibility of analysing both the lexical structure and cultural meaning of a text.

Thus, Wu's study is relevant to CLS objectives because it offers quantitative methods for analyzing linguistic complexity and cultural positioning of literary texts (Wu et al. 2024). This approach can be adapted to study historical shifts in language, style, and genre in literature, as well as to comparatively analyse canonical texts in different historical and cultural contexts.

Challenges of Using ChatGPT for Text Generation and Stylometry

Despite advancements in text generation and stylometry, ChatGPT and other language models face notable challenges. Studies on poetry generation and authorship attribution reveal issues related to limited creativity, reliance on repetitive patterns, and sensitivity to training data and query formulation. While LLMs can successfully mimic stylistic and structural features, their ability to generate truly novel or deeply coherent texts remains constrained (Walsh et al. 2024; Mikołajec 2024).

One of the most persistent problems in AI-generated poetry is its tendency toward predictability. Studies on AI poetry generation such as the one by Dai (2021) and by Walsh et al. (2024) show that generated texts often rely on recurring words and metaphors, making them formulaic. While models like GPT-4 can follow strict poetic forms such as sonnets and villanelles, they frequently struggle with more complex rhythmic and metrical patterns. Even when they successfully imitate formal constraints, the thematic depth and conceptual richness of human-authored poetry remain difficult to replicate.

Another major challenge is the dependence on prompt formulation. The quality of queries strongly influences the coherence and stylistic fidelity of generated texts. Poorly structured prompts often lead to outputs that fail to align with literary or genre-specific conventions (Mikołajec 2024). To address this, researchers have developed multi-step prompting techniques, but these require significant manual intervention, making fully automated generation impractical. Additionally, LLMs exhibit varying performance across languages, with studies on Polish poetry generation showing increased syntactic and stylistic errors due to tokenization difficulties and linguistic complexity (Walsh et al. 2024).

The quality of training data also plays a crucial role in generation and stylometric analysis. Dai's study (2021) highlights that working with a limited corpus led to overfitting, restricting the model's ability to produce original content. Conversely, larger models such as GPT-4 struggle to balance memorization with creativity. In stylometry, text length remains a limitation, as most methods require extensive textual input to detect authorial patterns, restricting their applicability to short excerpts or fragmented texts (Rebora 2023). Furthermore, when LLMs are trained on the same datasets used for analysis, there is a risk of data leakage, leading to biased results (Schmidt et al. 2024).

The use of perplexity as a metric for analyzing canonical texts, as explored by Wu et al. (2024), provides valuable insights but comes with interpretative challenges. High perplexity scores may reflect not only linguistic complexity but also model-specific limitations in handling unconventional literary styles. Additionally, perplexity values vary depending on the LLM architecture, complicating direct comparisons across different corpora.

Authorship attribution studies further expose a fundamental weakness in LLM-based stylometry: a tendency to prioritize semantic similarity over stylistic markers. Schmidt et al. (2024) found that in Latin texts, GPT-4o frequently misattributed authorship based on thematic content rather than linguistic style, even when explicitly instructed to focus on stylistic features. Attempts to guide models using historically informed prompts often reduced, rather than improved, accuracy. Similarly, Silva et al. (2024) show that while ChatGPT-generated texts can closely imitate an author's style, traditional attribution models struggle to distinguish genuine works from AI-generated forgeries. The Forged-GAN-BERT-model performed well in binary classification tasks but saw a decline in accuracy when dealing with multiple candidate authors, highlighting the challenge of scaling LLM-based attribution beyond controlled datasets.

Another challenge is the interpretability of LLM decisions. Unlike traditional stylometric methods that rely on obvious linguistic markers, LLMs function as complex neural networks, making their predictions less transparent (Schmidt et al. 2024). Even when correctly identifying stylistic features, their reasoning remains unclear. This, along with misinformation risks and copyright issues caused by AI-generated forgeries, raises concerns about the reliability of LLMs in scholarly applications, particularly in the attribution of historical or lesser-known texts (Silva et al. 2024; Schmidt et al. 2024).

These limitations underscore the need for refinement in LLM-based literary analysis. While ChatGPT offers promising capabilities, its effectiveness in text generation and

stylometry remains constrained by methodological challenges. Addressing these issues requires improvements in model adaptability, enhanced fine-tuning techniques, and more robust approaches to query formulation. Integrating LLMs with traditional stylometric methods could offer a more balanced approach, combining computational power with linguistic transparency (Rebora 2023). Despite current limitations, LLMs remain a valuable tool in Computational Literary Studies when applied with careful methodological consideration.

Literary Translation

ChatGPT demonstrated strong performance in text-related tasks. It is still being explored as a stand-alone translation tool with many advantages due to its interactive and dialogue structure. Using ChatGPT allows, for example, the explanation of the meaning of expressions or words in a certain context, including professional vocabulary or expressions from different cultural contexts. ChatGPT can also assist in tasks, which involve text comprehension and analysis, namely simplification of complex content, error detection, grammar or text quality checking, stylistic analysis of the text and, finally, translation (Siu 2023). Additionally, the latest GPT versions have the ability to perform tasks in multilingual contexts, allowing input in one language and output in another.

Among the strengths of using ChatGPT for translation purposes, S. C. Siu (2023) mentions its speed and cost-effectiveness, ability to generate creative text, high adaptability to the context and the possibility to feed the system additional information to correctly interpret text in order to improve output. However, there are also limitations, among which stand out the translation quality (in domain-specific topics ChatGPT handles worse than commercial systems), hallucinations and bias, the strong dependence of the output on the prompt, limitations by domain (some topics that ChatGPT considers “sensitive” may not be handled as well), and still limited support for languages like Chinese. In general, Siu (2023) views ChatGPT as a tool for a ‘translation revolution’ and speaks positively about the perspectives of its use in translation.

Nevertheless, translation of literary texts presents specific challenges. First of all, authorial creativity and the challenge of preserving stylistic features and nuances are key considerations. There is a wide range of translative techniques that people apply to translate literary text (Karpinska and Iyyer 2023). In the next section, examples of the application of ChatGPT to literary translation will be discussed.

Examples for Using GPT for Literary Translation

Some studies on the effectiveness of large language models are mentioned by Karpinska and Iyer (2023). The tests were mainly conducted on sentence-level and document-level translations. The researchers tested the effectiveness of GPT-3.5 on translating literary texts at the paragraph level. The study was conducted on 18 unique language pairs, including several source languages (e.g. Russian, Czech, French, German, Chinese) and three target languages (English, Polish and Japanese). The texts represented contemporary novels that were published after 2021. Twenty paragraphs consisting of dialogue and narrative texts were extracted and matched with corresponding paragraphs in the target languages. Language pairs were selected in such a way that their structural difference (Japanese-Polish) and similarity (Czech-Polish) were taken into account. Thus, the dataset consisted of 360 paragraphs.

The GPT-3.5 text-davinci-003 model was employed with a few-shot technique based on three translation strategies: SENT (sentence-level translation), PARA_SENT (sentences-level translation with paragraph context) and PARA (paragraph-level translation). The test involved human evaluators – 13 translators who were fluent in the respective languages. They checked the model outputs for span-level errors (e.g. mistranslation, consistency, grammar) and marked the best translations for each strategy using metrics for evaluating translation quality (such as COMET, BLEURT and BERTSCORE). The translation was also compared with the Google Translate result.

The most effective strategy was PARA, which provided smoother, more cohesive translations with better preservation of literary style and fewer errors in context-dependent elements. In addition, GPT was better at translating syntactic constructions, polysemy and cultural features (such as pronouns in Japanese) with this strategy. The SENT strategy (sentence-by-sentence translation) resulted in more mistranslations and issues with grammar and consistency. The sentence-by-sentence translation involving context from the paragraph (PARA_SENT) had the disadvantage of randomly repeating sentences. Overall, this approach performed better than translation via Google Translate, which showed significantly more grammar and translation errors. The authors attribute this to the fact that Google Translate translates all languages through English as a pivot language, which distorts the translation (Karpinska and Iyer 2023).

Rhetorical devices such as metaphors, rhyme and imagery, and how artificial intelligence can handle them, are the topic of research by I. Karabayeva and A. Kalizhanova (2024). The dataset was based on the English language works *Coraline* by

Neil Gaiman, from which 15 passages filled with creative rhetorical devices were extracted. They were translated using ChatGPT and DeepL into Russian and evaluated by human and automatic methods according to several criteria – accuracy, fluency and preservation of literary devices (Karabayeva and Kalizhanova 2024).

Both systems did well with plain text, with DeepL translations being more accurate in translation (grammatically coherent translation), but often provided a direct translation, without interpreting hidden metaphors. ChatGPT was better at metaphors and paraphrases, but it occasionally made grammatical errors, which it corrected itself when pointed out. In terms of literary devices, both systems succeeded with metaphors, although they had problems with the more obscure cases. While DeepL lost the vividness of expressions, ChatGPT performed better when provided additional guided instructions. Neither system successfully reproduced rhyme schemes or alliteration to match human translations. Despite the problems with cultural nuances, ChatGPT performed better than DeepL due to its interactivity and ability to provide additional guided instructions. However, the authors argue that a blended method, incorporating both automatic and manual translation techniques, can be the most effective solution (Karabayeva and Kalizhanova 2024).

Some languages, due to their nature, are difficult to be interpreted by a language model. Chinese, for instance, is a language that poses significant challenges for large language models (Siu 2023). Yu et al. tested a scenario of using ChatGPT on a Chinese-language dataset, the *Literary Fiction Evaluation Dataset* (Yu et al. 2024), specifically designed to test the effectiveness of the language model on long literary works. The dataset consisted of 95 novels in Chinese or translated into Chinese with a length of 30000 words or more, including various literary genres. Several language models – ChatGPT, ChatGLM-6B, BLOOM-560M, BLOOM-1B7, BELLE-7B (two variants) – participated in the test. The approach involved asking the models questions with and without additional contexts (few-shot and zero-shot), covering different literary aspects. The responses were then evaluated for book comprehension. Human experts were involved in the study and supervised the questions and the model's answers.

ChatGPT outperformed all other models, excelling particularly in questions about character development, personality traits and literary style. It performed weakest in the question category Counterfactual Reasoning, which is “a situation or description that does not align with a fiction, such as a false character relationship or an event that does not exist in the fiction” (Yu et al. 2024). The length of the work also affected the success of the performance, such that relatively short (under 100,000 characters) and very long (over 1 million characters) novels presented difficulties for the model due to a lack of

detail or an overabundance of detail. As the authors note, all models faced challenges in processing the complex relationships between events and characters in long Chinese texts. Literary texts with culturally specific elements and long narratives presented serious challenges for all models (Yu et al. 2024).

Challenges of ChatGPT in Literary Translation

The main challenge for ChatGPT when used to translate literary works is the complex literary elements that need to be transferred from one language to another, preserving the author's intent and adapting cultural and linguistic intricacies. Even the latest GPT models exhibit inaccuracies in translating low-resource languages, which is a consequence of the lack of sufficient tests on them. Karpinska and Iyer (2023) also talk about limitations on high- and mid-resource languages in some scenarios, such as inverted word order in German. They also point out the reduced efficiency of translation in certain domains, the need for human expertise and the heavy reliance on it. Much attention is paid to prompt design, including adapting the length and structure of prompts. This ensures that the final translation does not create artefacts that could distort the source text. These difficulties are noted across multiple studies, which implies the involvement of additional expertise and checks.

An important drawback of the language models used as automatic translators is their insufficient understanding of the context. Thus, when translating paragraphs of different language pairs, periodic omissions were observed, i.e. the exclusion of important details from the context, which affected accuracy. In addition, sentences with different subjects were occasionally merged, leading to incorrect attribution of actions or events (Karpinska and Iyer 2023).

Complex literary techniques are also challenging for ChatGPT and other translation systems such as DeepL. Such systems often struggle to convey creative nuances in literary language, resorting to simplification, misinterpretation, or excluding complex techniques from text. Hallucinations were also observed, as noted by Karabayeva and Kalizhanova (2024), in the form of irrelevant ideas that were excessively generated by ChatGPT during analyses and refinements, resulting in distorted translation results and narrative coherence.

Overall, ChatGPT cannot yet function as a stand-alone tool for automatic translation, as it needs fine-tuning and human expertise. However, at this stage, it is evident that most of the limitations are not critical, and ChatGPT, along with other large language models,

demonstrate great potential in this area, though primarily through combined methodology.

Limitations and Future Work

Limitations of ChatGPT in CLS

Nowadays ChatGPT is becoming an increasingly common tool for addressing CLS tasks. However, as we have seen in previous chapters, the use of artificial intelligence as a standalone tool presents some methodological and technical limitations. The studies we reviewed highlight several limitations of ChatGPT in processing literary texts, including insufficient text understanding and interpretation, limited knowledge, high sensitivity to prompts, data bias, and certain ethical risks. Let us examine these limitations in more detail.

One of the clearest indicators of ChatGPT's difficulty in accurately interpreting texts is its tendency to generate a large number of "hallucinations" – statements that appear plausible but are factually incorrect (Forbes 2023). This issue significantly complicates text analysis, especially in the context of CLS, where precise interpretation is essential. In addition to previous criticism of ChatGPT in this regard, Ziems et al. (2023) found that the model struggles with complex annotation tasks, such as categorizing characters according to 72 archetypal tropes. However, emotion categorization and stance detection show relatively high accuracy. ChatGPT also shows systematic problems with the processing of fiction texts and struggles with its specific structure. As Karabayeva & Kalizhanova (2024) note, ChatGPT loses rhythm and structure when analyzing poetry, which makes it difficult to use for stylistic analysis of literary works.

Literary research using ChatGPT has consistently highlighted its challenges in contextual understanding and reasoning. Due to its reliance on probabilistic word prediction rather than logical argumentation, the model struggles to analyze complex literary structures effectively (Forbes 2023; Schmidt et al. 2024). The inability to retain context over long passages makes these issues worse leading to fragmented and inconsistent analysis. While in-context learning improves the model's ability to generate literary text, it remains highly sensitive to data ordering (Lester et al. 2021). Combined with its tendency to generate redundant but plausible-sounding false information, and the well-documented dependence on slight variations in prompts, there's a risk of producing texts that appear correct but are in fact pseudoscientific nonsense.

Another significant limitation of ChatGPT, which slows down progress in literary research, is its restricted text-processing capacity. First, not all models, even those introduced as of January 2025, support file attachments. Second, even advanced versions like ChatGPT-4o have strict character limits, constraining the amount of text they can analyze in a single instance. As a result, the models are unable to process long works of fiction or entire literary corpora (Parigini et al. 2024). Even when employing chunking techniques to divide texts into smaller segments, the models tend to lose global narrative coherence, leading to inaccurate conclusions and distortions in large-scale literary analysis.

Another key issue is the lack of transparency regarding ChatGPT's training data, particularly the genre distribution of literary texts. While the model has been trained on a broad dataset that includes web context and books, specific details about its literary coverage remain undisclosed. As a result, the model's literary "horizon" is limited. Furthermore, according to Chang et al. (2023), ChatGPT appears to memorize only the most popular and frequently referenced online books (e.g. *Alice in Wonderland*, *Harry Potter* novels). The authors observe a direct correlation between a book's popularity and the likelihood that ChatGPT knows and can recognize it. The lack of transparency of training data sources and difficulty in remembering less popular literature could lead to biased and incomplete textual analysis.

As artificial intelligence research advances, ethical and legal concerns surrounding its applications are becoming increasingly urgent. Specialists have identified several key issues, including generation of false or toxic content, the lack of transparency in LLM's decision-making process, and potential copyright infringement. While these problems are widely recognized, they pose significant challenges for the use of ChatGPT and similar models in literary studies.

Future Directions

Taking into account all the discussed limitations, a number of studies propose concrete ways to improve the performance of ChatGPT. The following are the main directions on which current efforts to adapt and optimize the model for literary analysis are focused. Given these limitations, it is necessary to adapt ChatGPT for CLS tasks, and develop new methods to improve its accuracy and interpretability. One of the most accessible solutions currently available is optimization of prompting strategies. Studies such as Lu et al. (2023) propose prompt optimization techniques that have improved text classification performance by 13%. The authors successfully adapted iterative prompt

refinement to generate text in Lovecraft's style, demonstrating in-context learning as a viable strategy for literary text generation (Lu et al. 2023).

Many scholars emphasize the need for fine-tuned models specifically designed for literary analysis. Pagel et al. (2024) argue that adapting LLMs to fiction-specific corpora is necessary for improving their literary capabilities. However, fine-tuning requires access to specialized datasets, as the standard model may lack sufficient exposure to diverse literary works. Techniques such as PEFT (Parameter Efficient Fine-Tuning) and LoRA (Low-Rank Adaptation) allow for domain-specific model adaptations without the need for extensive retraining (Lester et al. 2021; Hu et al. 2021).

For more interpretable AI-based literary analysis, hybrid approaches are widely recommended. Combining ChatGPT with classical CLS methods and traditional NLP techniques represents a promising development path for improving model explainability and reducing errors. Schmidt et al. (2024) point out that integrating deep neural networks with classical text analysis algorithms can reduce the risk of misinterpretation and enhance the interpretability of AI-driven literary studies.

Finally, one rapidly growing research area is the detection of AI-generated fake texts. This field is gaining increasing importance not only for identifying fake news and AI-generated context but also for resolving authorship disputes and verifying textual authenticity. This, in particular, can be called one of the promising and important areas of computational literary research.

The transparency of LLMs' decision making process remains a challenging and unsolved issue. The challenge is to understand the logic behind ChatGPT's responses and which sources it references. ChatGPT has become a highly applicable tool in many domains, and it is important to increase the trustworthiness of its outputs. Explainable AI (XAI) could be a promising solution to that issue by improving the interpretability of AI-driven decisions. Kovari (2025) offers a review of existing research on XAI and its applications across different fields, such as medicine, design, and e-commerce, documenting methods that increase AI transparency. Among these, feature importance analysis (e.g. SHAP, LIME) helps identify which parts of the input influence the model's response. Special attention mechanisms reveal which words or phrases the model prioritizes. Additionally, example-based explanations provide users with similar past cases, helping to justify AI-generated outputs. Recently, reasoning models have been made available that purport to make their "reasoning" process when generating a response to a prompt transparent. These techniques can be applied to make LLMs more understandable and trustworthy.

Despite its limitations, ChatGPT remains a powerful tool for CLS. However, its effective application requires fine-tuning, optimization, and integration with traditional literary studies methodologies. The development of hybrid approaches, fine-tuning methods (LoRA, PEFT), and improved prompt engineering will significantly expand the potential of large language models in literary texts analysis. Looking ahead, the integration of specialized AI solutions with traditional digital humanities methodologies will define the future of artificial intelligence in Computational Literary Studies.

Conclusion

The integration of large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT into the field of Computational Literary Studies (CLS) creates new opportunities, but also poses a number of challenges. As shown in this study, ChatGPT demonstrates significant abilities in key CLS tasks including literary analysis, text generation, stylometry and translation. It is capable of identifying thematic patterns, analysing narrative structures and recognising stylistic features, making it a useful tool for analysing large literary corpora. The model is able to generate stylistically consistent texts and perform authorship attribution, which makes it an effective tool for stylometric studies. ChatGPT can effectively capture text coherence and fluency and can serve as a supporting tool in literary translation. However, in all these areas, the model's performance is still limited by its architectural weaknesses, raising questions about accuracy, interpretability and methodological robustness.

Despite its potential, the limitations of ChatGPT require a careful strategic approach to its use in CLS. As the studies show, the model is still very sensitive to prompt formulation and has a tendency to generate “hallucinations”. A major drawback is its inability to fully analyse long texts. It shows that ChatGPT cannot yet act as a stand-alone tool for literary analysis. In addition, the opacity of the model training data highlights concerns about possible bias in its outputs, uneven genre coverage and underrepresentation of less popular literary works. These aspects emphasise the importance of combining AI methods with traditional CLS approaches rather than replacing existing methodologies with them.

In the future, researchers should focus on adapting LLMs to specific literary tasks by developing pre-trained models based on specially selected literary corpora. Various methods such as LoRA (Low-Rank Adaptation) and PEFT (Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning) can help for ChatGPT optimisation without the need for complete model retraining. Additionally, hybrid methods that combine deep learning with traditional

stylometry and statistical analysis can improve the interpretability and reproducibility of CLS research.

Beyond technical improvements, the increasing use of AI in CLS brings attention to important issues regarding the relationship between human and machine analysis. While ChatGPT undoubtedly improves research in CLS, it also challenges traditional ideas and approaches. In particular, ChatGPT changes how we understand authorship, interpretation, and literary criticism. It generates texts in different styles, suggests meanings based on patterns, and offers analysis that does not rely on human experience. As these models continue to evolve, it is important to ensure accuracy, transparency, and ethical use in academic work. Artificial intelligence should not replace human interpretation of literary texts, but can be a tool that supports and extends traditional methods of literary analysis. However, its application requires control, constant refinement and a thoughtful approach.

References

- Beltagy, Iz, et al. Longformer: The Long-Document Transformer. arXiv:2004.05150, arXiv, 2 Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2004.05150>.
- Brown, Tom B., Benjamin Mann, Nick Ryder, Melanie Subbiah, Jared Kaplan, Prafulla Dhariwal, Arvind Neelakantan, et al. "Language Models Are Few-Shot Learners," 2020. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2005.14165>.
- Chang, Kent K., Mackenzie Cramer, Sandeep Soni, and David Bamman. "Speak, Memory: An Archaeology of Books Known to ChatGPT/GPT-4," 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2305.00118>.
- Chowdhery, Aakanksha, Sharan Narang, Jacob Devlin, Maarten Bosma, Gaurav Mishra, Adam Roberts, Paul Barham, et al. "PaLM: Scaling Language Modeling with Pathways." arXiv, October 5, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2204.02311>.
- Dai, Alice. "GPT-2 for Emily Dickinson Poetry Generation," 2021. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/GPT-2-for-Emily-Dickinson-poetry-generation-Dai/c9b413ad7d559b6598b925cd4b8e4d7fd2dcc53>.
- Dejaeghere, Tess, Pranaydeep Singh, Els Lefever, and Julie Birkholz. "Exploring Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis Methodologies for Literary-Historical Research Purposes." In *Proceedings of the Third Workshop on Language Technologies for Historical and Ancient Languages (LT4HALA) @ LREC-COLING-2024*, edited by Rachele Sprugnoli and Marco Passarotti, 129–43. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL, 2024. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.lt4hala-1.16>.

- Devlin, Jacob, Ming-Wei Chang, Kenton Lee, and Kristina Toutanova. "BERT: Pre-Training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding." arXiv, May 24, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1810.04805>.
- Fröhling, Leon, and Arkaitz Zubiaga. "Feature-Based Detection of Automated Language Models: Tackling GPT-2, GPT-3 and Grover." *PeerJ Computer Science* 7 (April 6, 2021): e443. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.443>.
- He, Pengcheng, Xiaodong Liu, Jianfeng Gao, and Weizhu Chen. "DeBERTa: Decoding-Enhanced BERT with Disentangled Attention." arXiv, October 6, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2006.03654>.
- Hicke, Rebecca M. M., Yuri Bizzoni, Pascale Feldkamp, and R. Kristensen-Mclachlan. "Says Who? Effective Zero-Shot Annotation of Focalization," 2024. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Says-Who-Effective-Zero-Shot-Annotation-of-Hicke-Bizzoni/b08ae12e2b30d9c41788f1f7ed077756787b4ee2>.
- Hicke, Rebecca M. M., and David Mimno. "T5 Meets Tybalt: Author Attribution in Early Modern English Drama Using Large Language Models." arXiv, October 27, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2310.18454>.
- Hochreiter, Sepp, and Jürgen Schmidhuber. "Long Short-Term Memory." *Neural Computation* 9, no. 8 (November 1, 1997): 1735–80. <https://doi.org/10.1162/neco.1997.9.8.1735>.
- Hoffmann, Jordan, Sebastian Borgeaud, Arthur Mensch, Elena Buchatskaya, Trevor Cai, Eliza Rutherford, Diego de Las Casas, et al. "Training Compute-Optimal Large Language Models." arXiv, March 29, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.15556>.
- Hu, Edward J., Yelong Shen, Phillip Wallis, Zeyuan Allen-Zhu, Yuanzhi Li, Shean Wang, Lu Wang, and Weizhu Chen. "LoRA: Low-Rank Adaptation of Large Language Models." arXiv, October 16, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2106.09685>.
- Huang, Baixiang, Canyu Chen, and Kai Shu. "Authorship Attribution in the Era of LLMs: Problems, Methodologies, and Challenges." arXiv, January 9, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2408.08946>.
- Kalchbrenner, Nal, Edward Grefenstette, and Phil Blunsom. "A Convolutional Neural Network for Modelling Sentences." arXiv, April 8, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1404.2188>.
- Kalyan, Katikapalli Subramanyam. "A Survey of GPT-3 Family Large Language Models Including ChatGPT and GPT-4." *Natural Language Processing Journal* 6 (2024): 100048. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nlp.2023.100048>.

- Karabayeva, Irina, and Anna Kalizhanova. "Evaluating Machine Translation of Literature through Rhetorical Analysis." *Journal of Translation and Language Studies* 5, no. 1 (January 12, 2024): 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.48185/jtls.v5i1.962>.
- Karpinska, Marzena, and Mohit Iyer. "Large Language Models Effectively Leverage Document-Level Context for Literary Translation, but Critical Errors Persist." [object Object], 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2304.03245>.
- Kovari, Attila. "Explainable AI Chatbots towards XAI ChatGPT: A Review." *Heliyon* 11, no. 2 (January 30, 2025): e42077. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2025.e42077>.
- Kuzman, Taja, Igor Mozetič, and Nikola Ljubešić. "ChatGPT: Beginning of an End of Manual Linguistic Data Annotation? Use Case of Automatic Genre Identification." arXiv, March 8, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.03953>.
- Lan, Zhenzhong, Mingda Chen, Sebastian Goodman, Kevin Gimpel, Piyush Sharma, and Radu Soricut. "ALBERT: A Lite BERT for Self-Supervised Learning of Language Representations." arXiv, February 9, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1909.11942>.
- Le Mens, Gaël, Balázs Kovács, Michael T. Hannan, and Guillem Pros. "Uncovering the Semantics of Concepts Using GPT-4." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 120, no. 49 (December 5, 2023): e2309350120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2309350120>.
- Lee, Ariel N., Cole J. Hunter, and Nataniel Ruiz. "Platypus: Quick, Cheap, and Powerful Refinement of LLMs." arXiv, March 14, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2308.07317>.
- Lester, Brian, Rami Al-Rfou, and Noah Constant. "The Power of Scale for Parameter-Efficient Prompt Tuning." arXiv, September 2, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2104.08691>.
- Lewis, Mike, Yinhan Liu, Naman Goyal, Marjan Ghazvininejad, Abdelrahman Mohamed, Omer Levy, Ves Stoyanov, and Luke Zettlemoyer. "BART: Denoising Sequence-to-Sequence Pre-Training for Natural Language Generation, Translation, and Comprehension." arXiv, October 29, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1910.13461>.
- Liu, Yinhan, Myle Ott, Naman Goyal, Jingfei Du, Mandar Joshi, Danqi Chen, Omer Levy, Mike Lewis, Luke Zettlemoyer, and Veselin Stoyanov. "RoBERTa: A Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach." arXiv, July 26, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1907.11692>.
- Mikołajec, Marek. "Sztuczna Inteligencja w Świetle Humanistyki Cyfrowej i Literaturoznawstwa/Artificial Intelligence in the Light of Digital Humanities Literary and Studies." *Media i Społeczeństwo*, January 1, 2024. https://www.academia.edu/124725184/Sztuczna_inteligencja_w_%C5%9Bwietle_humanistyki_cyfrowej_i_literaturoznawstwa_Artificial_Intelligence_in_the_Light_of_Digital_Humanities_Literary_and_Studies.

- Mikros, George K., Athanasios Koursaris, Dimitrios Bilianos, and George Markopoulos. "AI-Writing Detection Using an Ensemble of Transformers and Stylometric Features," 2023.
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/AI-Writing-Detection-Using-an-Ensemble-of-and-Mikros-Koursaris/bb8741671e05015f0f67fd6e4f66ae5cf1cc0f7e>.
- OpenAI, Josh Achiam, Steven Adler, Sandhini Agarwal, Lama Ahmad, Ilge Akkaya, Florencia Leoni Aleman, et al. "GPT-4 Technical Report." arXiv, March 4, 2024.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.08774>.
- Ouyang, Long, Jeff Wu, Xu Jiang, Diogo Almeida, Carroll L. Wainwright, Pamela Mishkin, Chong Zhang, et al. "Training Language Models to Follow Instructions with Human Feedback." arXiv, March 4, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.02155>.
- Pagel, Janis, Axel Pichler, and Nils Reiter. "Evaluating In-Context Learning for Computational Literary Studies: A Case Study Based on the Automatic Recognition of Knowledge Transfer in German Drama." In *Proceedings of the 8th Joint SIGHUM Workshop on Computational Linguistics for Cultural Heritage, Social Sciences, Humanities and Literature (LaTeCH-CLfL 2024)*, edited by Yuri Bizzoni, Stefania Degaetano-Ortlieb, Anna Kazantseva, and Stan Szpakowicz, 1–10. St. Julians, Malta: Association for Computational Linguistics, 2024. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.latechclfl-1.1>.
- Qin, Chengwei, Aston Zhang, Zhuosheng Zhang, Jiaao Chen, Michihiro Yasunaga, and Diyi Yang. "Is ChatGPT a General-Purpose Natural Language Processing Task Solver?," 2023.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2302.06476>.
- Radford, Alec, and Karthik Narasimhan. "Improving Language Understanding by Generative Pre-Training," 2018.
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Improving-Language-Understanding-by-Generative-Pre-Training-Radford-Narasimhan/cd18800a0fe0b668a1cc19f2ec95b5003d0a5035>.
- Radford, Alec, Jeff Wu, R. Child, D. Luan, Dario Amodei, and I. Sutskever. "Language Models Are Unsupervised Multitask Learners," 2019.
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Language-Models-are-Unsupervised-Multitask-Learners-Radford-Wu/9405cc0d6169988371b2755e573cc28650d14dfe>.
- Rebora, Simone. "GPT-3 vs. Delta. Applying Stylometry to Large Language Models," 2023.
<https://iris.univr.it/handle/11562/1115882>.
- S. GARRET RAJA IMMANUEL, and P. NEVEDHA LIZ GLORIA. "AI-Driven Literary Analysis: Exploring the Role of ChatGPT in Understanding and Interpreting Literary Texts." *Bodhi International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Science* 8, no. 2 (January 2024). https://www.bodhijournals.com/pdf/V8N2/Bodhi_V8N2_009.pdf.

- Salehinejad, Hojjat, Sharan Sankar, Joseph Barfett, Errol Colak, and Shahrokh Valaee. “Recent Advances in Recurrent Neural Networks.” arXiv, February 22, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1801.01078>.
- Sap, Maarten, Eric Horvitz, Yejin Choi, Noah A. Smith, and James Pennebaker. “Recollection versus Imagination: Exploring Human Memory and Cognition via Neural Language Models.” In *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 1970–78. Online: Association for Computational Linguistics, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.178>.
- Schmidt, Gleb, Svetlana Gorovaia, and Ivan P. Yamshchikov. “Sui Generis: Large Language Models for Authorship Attribution and Verification in Latin.” arXiv, October 11, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.09245>.
- Schuster, Tal, Roei Schuster, Darsh J. Shah, and Regina Barzilay. “The Limitations of Stylometry for Detecting Machine-Generated Fake News.” *Computational Linguistics* 46, no. 2 (2020): 499–510. https://doi.org/10.1162/coli_a_00380.
- Silva, Kanishka, Ingo Frommholz, Burcu Can, Fred Blain, Raheem Sarwar, and Laura Ugolini. “Forged-GAN-BERT: Authorship Attribution for LLM-Generated Forged Novels.” In *Proceedings of the 18th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Student Research Workshop*, edited by Neele Falk, Sara Papi, and Mike Zhang, 325–37. St. Julian’s, Malta: Association for Computational Linguistics, 2024. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.eacl-srw.26/>.
- Siu, Sai Cheong. “ChatGPT and GPT-4 for Professional Translators: Exploring the Potential of Large Language Models in Translation.” *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4448091>.
- Thoppilan, Romal, Daniel De Freitas, Jamie Hall, Noam Shazeer, Apoorv Kulshreshtha, Heng-Tze Cheng, Alicia Jin, et al. “LaMDA: Language Models for Dialog Applications.” arXiv, February 10, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2201.08239>.
- Touvron, Hugo, Thibaut Lavril, Gautier Izacard, Xavier Martinet, Marie-Anne Lachaux, Timothée Lacroix, Baptiste Rozière, et al. “LLaMA: Open and Efficient Foundation Language Models.” arXiv, February 27, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.13971>.
- Touvron, Hugo, Louis Martin, Kevin Stone, Peter Albert, Amjad Almahairi, Yasmine Babaei, Nikolay Bashlykov, et al. “Llama 2: Open Foundation and Fine-Tuned Chat Models.” arXiv, July 19, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2307.09288>.
- Troiano, Enrica, and Piek Vossen. “CLAUSE-ATLAS: A Corpus of Narrative Information to Scale up Computational Literary Analysis,” 2024.

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/CLAUSE-ATLAS%3A-A-Corpus-of-Narrative-Information-to-Troiano-Vossen/1fd4668115dcbec2fa09ff7379a90cc4db325495>.

Underwood, Ted. “Can Language Models Predict the next Twist in a Story?” *The Stone and the Shell* (blog), January 5, 2024. <https://tedunderwood.com/2024/01/05/can-language-models-predict-the-next-twist-in-a-story/>.

———. “Using GPT-4 to Measure the Passage of Time in Fiction.” *The Stone and the Shell* (blog), March 19, 2023. <https://tedunderwood.com/2023/03/19/using-gpt-4-to-measure-the-passage-of-time-in-fiction/>.

Walsh, Melanie, Anna Preus, and Elizabeth Gronski. “Does ChatGPT Have a Poetic Style?” arXiv, October 30, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.15299>.

Wu, Yaru, Yuri Bizzoni, Pascale Moreira, and Kristoffer Nielbo. “Perplexing Canon: A Study on GPT-Based Perplexity of Canonical and Non-Canonical Literary Works.” In *Proceedings of the 8th Joint SIGHUM Workshop on Computational Linguistics for Cultural Heritage, Social Sciences, Humanities and Literature (LaTeCH-CLfL 2024)*, edited by Yuri Bizzoni, Stefania Degaetano-Ortlieb, Anna Kazantseva, and Stan Szpakowicz, 172–84. St. Julians, Malta: Association for Computational Linguistics, 2024. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.latechclfl-1.16/>.

Yang, Zhilin, Zihang Dai, Yiming Yang, Jaime Carbonell, Ruslan Salakhutdinov, and Quoc V. Le. “XLNet: Generalized Autoregressive Pretraining for Language Understanding.” arXiv, January 2, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1906.08237>.

Yu, Linhao, Qun Liu, and Deyi Xiong. “LFED: A Literary Fiction Evaluation Dataset for Large Language Models.” [object Object], 2024. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2405.10166>.

Zhao, Wayne Xin, Kun Zhou, Junyi Li, Tianyi Tang, Xiaolei Wang, Yupeng Hou, Yingqian Min, et al. “A Survey of Large Language Models.” arXiv, November 24, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.18223>.

Linked Open Data As The Way To Go For Literary Character Analysis?

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Introduction

It did not take long for Linked Open Data technologies to be incorporated into Literary Studies. Projects have been modeling literary data as graphs and networks for over twenty years, even longer, if taking into account all these projects which follow a more traditional network analysis approach (for examples see section “Use Cases”). Looking beyond modeling character relations with SNA, however, the interest in and use of Linked Open Data technologies for example to analyze literary characters, in other ways than looking at their relations, seems to be significantly lower. Or rather, for a long time it remained sporadic, with smaller projects applying said technologies to their limited scope and too often without making their data models accessible. One example that would have been of interest for this analysis is the ontology for characters in folktales developed by Thierry Declerck and differing co-researchers in the 2010s (Declerck et al. 2012, Declerck et al. 2017). Only snippets of the ontology are shown in the publications, preventing evaluation and possible further use. This already proves again the importance of open data, whether linked or not. In general, there did and does not seem to be a lack of interest in literary characters but rather in Linked Open Data technologies as a means of analyzing the former. In 2023, Hoque et al. asked five literary scholars about their way of analyzing a literary work and the characters appearing in it. While five persons certainly do not make for a representative study, it is still notable that all five still seemed to prefer close reading as a method and “were not aware of any tools [nor seemingly of any digital methods] for helping them in this process”. Things are already changing, though. Availability is not an issue with more recent ontologies, and projects applying Linked Open Data methods are on the rise as well.⁶

Use Cases of Character Data

For which aspects of Computational Literary Studies has character data so far been relevant? In which projects, especially newer ones, are they at the centre of research?

⁶ Many thanks to Maria Hinzmann for several fruitful conversations on modeling questions and literary theory.

In answer to the first question, a variety of character data and traits come into focus. Often enough, character data is collected and analyzed comprehensively, as seen in Bullard and Ovesdotter-Alm 2014 or Cheng 2020. Also, as said before, network analysis has been popular for decades, which is based mostly on character relation data, or, in case of a more statistical approach, on centrality measures and others (see Beveridge and Shan 2016, to name just one). Especially famous for its application to Literary Studies (though not as Linked Open Data) is Moretti 2011, but Social Network Analysis (SNA) was already present in the literary studies in 2002, when Alberich et al applied it to the Marvel universe. An early precursor of the method might even be found in a study from 1973 (see the short overview on literary network analysis in Trilcke 2013). Annotating data manually and therefore semantically does not seem to be too common.

A high interest can be noted for studies conducted on research questions with a gender angle, whether they focus specifically on the treatment of characters' gender in the literary works (among others Freitas and Santos 2024) or the analysis of a (not per se gender-related) research question is carried out in a gender-sensitive way. Studies like these depend therefore on gender as another aspect of character data. This is true as well for more loosely related questions, like the one about conversation topics of female characters posed by Agarwal et al. 2015, for research on gender hierarchies (Kraicer and Piper 2019), the representation of mothers in certain corpora, for gendered social structures in general (Cermáková and Mahlberg 2021), for gendered body language (Cermáková and Mahlberg 2022) and many more aspects.

Character traits are another important aspect of character, which is being analyzed since before 2016. McGill University's .txtlab, directed by Andrew Piper, looked at signs for introversion and extraversion in 2016.⁷ On a more general level, David Bamman und colleagues (Bamman et al. 2014) introduced an approach for identifying latent so-called "personas" as early as 2014, which was based on previous works of both others and the authors themselves even then. Piper 2023, in turn, pays particular attention to the agency of characters. The complexity of literary characters is being addressed, for example, by Braun et al. 2018.

It is also common to focus on a few selected aspects of characters which are considered in their respective interactions, while other aspects fade into the background: One example is the work already mentioned by Cermáková and Mahlberg 2022, which considers the characters' body language depending on their gender.

⁷ <https://txtlab.org/2016/04/why-are-jane-austens-novels-so-popular-her-characters-are-introverts/>.

Apart from the data mentioned above, central for certain research questions, other types of data, while not part of the main question, are no less relevant. At the same time, these data are not necessarily the focus of analysis. Among these are character names as identifiers of a character that, as such, are almost always of importance, nearly independently of the angle or topic of research. Of similarly common importance is the age of a character. For Cheng (Cheng 2020, p. 14), data on descriptions of body are also of interest, while not a core aspect of the research question. Notable exceptions among the generally important data are the characters' sex and, insofar as the differentiation is made in the texts examined, their gender, due to the high interest of research in gender-related research topics.

Linked Open Data for the Computational Literary Studies

What could be the use of Linked Open Data for the Computational Literary Studies, especially when working with literary characters, “named entities, literary historiographical data and corpus data itself” (as stated in the CLS INFRA project proposal)?

Literary historiographical data, and analysis conducted on it, probably includes the study by Maria Levchenko (University of Bologna), which she presented at the Graphs & Networks Conference in Mendrisio in February 2025 in her talk “Literary communities in St. Petersburg 1999-2019”.⁸ Works like hers show the benefits of Linked Open Data in working with literary historiographical data. Then again, in crossing over from literary history to historical prosopographical research in general, graph databases have been well established for years. Data on real and (once) living persons lends itself very well to being structured as a graph of relations, be it the relation of a person to their friends, colleagues or family, their occupation, place of work or residence or to their literary works. Consequently, there is an ample amount of models for dealing with data of persons and person networks. One of the more influential is the Factoid Prosopography Ontology (FPO) developed in the UK, at King's College London (Pasin & Bradley 2015), on which numerous prosopographical projects have based their data models (e.g. People of Medieval Scotland, poms.ac.uk; Prosopography of Anglo-Saxon England, pase.ac.uk; Nuns and Monks - Prosopographical Interfaces, data.nampi.icar-us.eu/). A standard even, at least for cultural heritage data, is the Conceptual Reference Model of the CIDOC working group (CIDOC CRM).⁹

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<https://graphentechnologien.hypotheses.org/tagungen/graphs-networks-conference-2025/conference-programme-2025>.

⁹ <https://cidoc-crm.org/>.

This suggests that modeling literary character data as a graph might be equally useful. After all, since literary characters, even non-human ones, usually possess at least anthropomorphic qualities and abilities, the way their data can be structured could be assumed to have many parallels.

On the other hand, there are several important differences between literary characters and persons, not limited by far to the fact that literary characters can be non-human. The foremost being that even the definition of what a literary character is (and where it therefore ought to be placed in the hierarchy of ontology classes) differs, according to the literary theory used to answer it. Which poses a challenge: Models designed with (once) living persons in mind are not necessarily appropriate for modeling literary characters. But to which extent is it even possible to build complete ontologies for (Computational) Literary Studies without contradictions? “Complete” meaning that they lead from a domain-specific level back to the most general class existing, like the class “Thing” in OWL, or the classes “E1 CRM Entity” in CIDOC-CRM or “entity (Q35120)” in Wikidata. Since there are different theories on how to define a literary character (see Eder et al. 2010), such an undertaking seems not only hard to implement, but also of dubious usefulness – at least if trying to develop a generally valid ontology that claims to model literary data up to the most general level (this being the class “owl:Thing” in OWL, to name just one). Ontologies as a concept of information science, strictly understood, make statements about logical relations between elements. Therefore, it is a constant challenge to condense complex and often contradicting real-world concepts and relations into a logically consistent model – a challenge that also extends to modeling different and at times contradicting literary theories. Structures for meta-statements would need to be included. Redundance for modeling literary characters after two different theories would have to be allowed for. A way to circumvent this can be to simply not model the more general “upper” ontological levels, as can be seen later on in the example of the character ontology of the *Noctua literaria* project.¹⁰ However, this also means that the ontology remains incomplete in that adding any set of superclasses would come with at least a few properties of their own. Subclasses inherit the properties of their superclasses, so not completing the ontology neglects to offer these kinds of relations. This leads to complications if one such “incomplete” character data model is to be embedded in an existing ontology that was not originally tailored to fit literary theory. Attempts to this end have been made for example by fitting literary theory model into the CIDOC CRM data model,¹¹ which has originally been designed for

¹⁰ <https://www.figurenontologie.de/>.

¹¹ E.g. by OntoPoetry, see Gonzalez-BlancoApplying2022 and GolemLab, see <https://github.com/GOLEM-lab/golem-ontology>.

cultural heritage data. While this works well enough for representing bibliographic metadata and biographic information on the authors, it does not seem ideal for representing literary works on content level.

Existing Ontologies

As previously mentioned in passing, attempts to model literary data with Linked Open Data technologies have already been made. But they often focus on the metadata, structure or any other data on formal, structural, analytical or meta-levels. They mostly neglect to represent the texts at the level of content. One example for a well thought-out ontology, that does, however, not cover the content level, is the OntoPoetry ontology. It was developed between 2015 and 2020 in the POSTDATA project.¹²

The OntoPoetry ontology was designed with the aim to build a common ontology for the needs of different european research communities.¹³ It consists of several modules for different “knowledge areas”. As the main use cases the project identified a) bibliographic information search and indexing and b) poetic information annotation and searching.¹⁴ It does not, however, address questions pertaining to literary characters and therefore does not offer sufficient coverage for this “knowledge area”, to gratefully adopt this term used by the project itself here. The relevant core classes are, self-explanatory, Person for “real persons who live or are assumed to have lived”¹⁵, and Character for “fictional or iconographic individuals or groups of individual appearing in works in a way relevant as subjects”¹⁶. The “Person”-class is modeled in a reasonably detailed manner, with properties to connect – among others – the names, important life dates, origin and occupation. There is no comparable amount of options for literary characters. They can be assigned a type and can be linked to a literary work, that is all. Other modules focus “especially on rhetorical figures or figure of speech such as tropes and schemes”¹⁷ or on bibliographical information¹⁸.

More interesting for the use cases in question is the already mentioned Noctua literaria system for the description and manipulation of literary characters.¹⁹ Designed as early as the 2000’s, according to the project-related publications,²⁰ it already offers many

¹² <https://postdata.linhd.uned.es/>.

¹³ <https://postdata.linhd.uned.es/results/network-of-ontologies/>.

¹⁴ <https://postdata.linhd.uned.es/results/ontopoetry-v2-0/>.

¹⁵ <https://postdata.linhd.uned.es/ontology/postdata-core/documentation/index-en.html#Person>.

¹⁶ <https://postdata.linhd.uned.es/ontology/postdata-core/documentation/index-en.html#Character>.

¹⁷ <https://postdata.linhd.uned.es/OntoPoetry/Poetic/documentation/index-en.html>.

¹⁸ <https://postdata.linhd.uned.es/OntoPoetry/Transmission/documentation/index-en.html>.

¹⁹ <https://www.figurenontologie.de/>.

²⁰ <https://www.figurenontologie.de/help.html>.

important features for literary character modeling. Among them are a class for statements about the analysed character, for character features (split into “inside” and “outward”) as well as character acts (split into “speech and thought” and “action and behaviour”).²¹ A list of classes is available, although offered without a description for any of them.²² Among them are several which are more generally applicable, like `on_age`, `on11_emotion` or `on_name_or_title`. Others seem curiously specific, like `on17_omniscience`, `on23_only_body` or `on58_urge_to_seduce`. This seems to be a result of the ontology being designed to fit one very narrow corpus only, namely several versions of the “Faust” or “Dr Faustus”-topic (Zöllner-Weber 2007). Stripped of the Faust-specific elements, only a very basic ontology remains for potential transfer onto other literary studies research topics.

For those not looking for a complete ontology, the use of Wikidata “classes” might be attractive as well. They are far from being consistent, although Wikidata strives to at least root out contradictions. It appears to be especially hard to contain redundant classes, though.

Another, practical, approach regarding the different needs of projects and researchers for studying different genres or even just different research topics regarding the data model seems to be modularity, as already found out by the aforementioned POSTDATA project.

A modular design is used as well by the more recent “Mining and Modeling Text” project (MiMoText, 2019-2023), which furthermore relies on a Wikibase infrastructure to model the data on the history of french novels as Linked Open Data (Schöch et al 2022, Hinzmann et al. 2024).²³ Like OntoPoetry, though, its main focus is on bibliographic data, and furthermore on the analysis of narratives, topics and stylometry, not offering a module specifically for literary characters.²⁴

The most recent approach, based on research of fanfictions, is the Golem Ontology. Developed by the “Graphs and Ontologies for Literary Evolution Models” project, in short GOLEM,²⁵ it also uses a modular approach. The Golem Ontology does contain a character module, providing a class for “`gc:G17_Character_Feature`” for physical, psychological and biographical features, as the GOLEM team structures them, and a unique class called “Character-Stoff”, which “encompasses the complete range of

²¹ https://www.figurenontologie.de/free_mind/mindmaps.html.

²² <https://www.figurenontologie.de/listofclasses.html>.

²³ <https://mimotext.uni-trier.de/english/>.

²⁴ <https://github.com/MiMoText/ontology>.

²⁵ <https://golemlab.eu/>.

representations and interpretations of a character, including their features, actions, relationships, and roles across all possible narratives and fictions”.²⁶ The character can be assigned a type and connected to a work. As of March 2025, this is the Golem ontology’s current implementation, although it has to be said that the project is still running until 2027, and the ontology will likely experience several changes until then.

Wikibase for Modeling Literary Characters: Pilot Study

Against the background of this state of the art, and in order to better understand the chances and challenges of modeling literary character data with Linked Open Data, a small pilot study was conducted. For this study, Wikibase was used. Wikibase is low-threshold and, if used in the Wikibase Cloud, does not even need to be self-hosted, which is probably the best offer for sustainable open data management available for single researchers and small projects. Also, since it uses the Wikidata structure of items and properties, this somewhat facilitates keeping one’s own data in the Wikibase aligned with Wikidata. Generally, this kind of alignment is not as easy as might be expected given the close relation between the two products, since Wikibase comes without any predefined items or properties. If one wishes, every class and property can be defined freely, without regard to existing Wikidata items. Only the lack of differentiation between classes and instances is shared by both Wikidata and individual Wikibase instances, both being combined into “items”. In this pilot study, however, the names and definitions of the “classes” and properties follow those already present in Wikidata wherever possible, in part to test to which extent this is feasible.

The data used was taken from Neuer Deutscher Novellenschatz (1884–1887), in the version provided by Deutsches Textarchiv (DTA).²⁷ From this corpus, the three novellas “Wer” by Ida von Düringsfeld, “Krambambuli” by Marie von Ebner-Eschenbach and “Eine schwarze Kugel” by A[mélie] Godin were chosen because of the modeling problems they present. The main question in “Wer” is to what extent a person’s own free will can influence or be influenced by that of another. It toes the line to the supernatural in suggesting that the will (and personality) of the mentally stronger person can erase the will and personality of the weaker one, leading, so to speak, to a personality transfer. Still, the line to the supernatural is never fully crossed. A definite answer as to whether the suspected personality transfer did indeed happen in the story is never given. This presents two challenges for modeling this novel: How would such a transfer be represented? And since it is kept deliberately open whether or not the transfer did

²⁶ <https://github.com/GOLEM-lab/golem-ontology/wiki/Character-Module>.

²⁷ <https://www.deutschestextarchiv.de/>.

happen at all, this ambiguity would have to be contained in the model as well. Therefore the transfer would have to be included as an event, to which not only the supposed perpetrator and victim would be connected, but also information on how plausible it is deemed to be by the characters. The changed character features of the supposed victim (of the supposed perpetrator remained only his dead body) would need to be added to his character data, but true only since after the transfer event, while his former personality features would need to be marked as no longer valid. That this sort of event is generally thought of as impossible in the novel as well and is intended to break this common logic, however, seems to go beyond what an ontology can represent.

“Krambambuli” and “Eine schwarze Kugel” contain each a central non-human entity. In “Krambambuli”, this is the dog after which the novel is titled. This illustrates the rather basic, but still important fact that any general ontology for the CLS should not limit a “literary character”-class to persons. The black ball in “Eine schwarze Kugel”, on the other hand, is not a character, it does not think or act or give any indication of being more than a simple, real-world billiard ball. It is an important enough object, though, to be included in a literary data model. Which leads to the question of whether real-world object classes can be used to model literary objects, or more generally, how and to what extent do literary worlds have to be modeled separately or can be explained by using properties and classes defined for real-world entities and relations? While there is a relatively large overlap between the three novellas chosen for this study and real-world 18th-to-19th-century Europe (mostly Germany), and on the surface, there would be no noticeable logical conflict in applying the same properties to the black billiard ball as to any real-world billiard ball, this overlap gets significantly smaller when moving to mythological or fantasy texts. This shows one important hurdle for a universal CLS model: There is no limit to the rules authors can introduce in their texts, to the worlds and realities they can create, the times in which they can let their plot play out. While a universal data model for the CLS does seem useful to further Linked Open Data, this model will have to stay general, with different, more specific modules to add as needed for the different genres and fictional worlds.

Data

The Wikibase instance containing the study data is accessible here: https://cls-infra-character-model.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Main_Page.

References

- Agarwal, Apoorv, et al. “Key Female Characters in Film Have More to Talk About Besides Men: Automating the Bechdel Test”. Proceedings of the 2015 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, 2015, pp. 830–40. <https://aclanthology.org/N15-1084.pdf>.
- Alberich, R., et al. Marvel Universe looks almost like a real social network. Preprint, arXiv, 2002. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.cond-mat/0202174>.
- Bamman, David, et al. “A Bayesian Mixed Effects Model of Literary Character”. Proceedings of the 52nd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers), Association for Computational Linguistics, 2014, pp. 370–79. <https://doi.org/10.3115/v1/P14-1035>.
- Beveridge, Andrew, and Jie Shan. “Network of Thrones”. Math Horizons Magazine, vol. 23, 4, 2016, pp. 18–22.
- Braun, Manuel, et al. Digitale Modellierung von Figurenkomplexität am Beispiel des Parzival von Wolfram von Eschenbach. 2018, [dhd2018_079](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-90799-9_79).
- Bullard, Joseph, and Cecilia Ovesdotter Alm. “Computational analysis to explore authors’ depiction of characters”. Proceedings of the 3rd workshop on computational linguistics for literature (CLFL), Association for Computational Linguistics, 2014, pp. 11–16, <https://doi.org/10.3115/v1/W14-0902>.
- Cermáková, Anna, and Michaela Mahlberg. “Gendered body language in children’s literature over time”. Language and Literature, no. 31, 2022, pp. 11–40, <https://doi.org/10.1177/09639470211072154>.
- . “The representation of mothers and the gendered social structure of nineteenth-century children’s literature”. English Text Construction, no. 14, 2021, pp. 119–49, <https://doi.org/10.1075/etc.00044.cer>.
- Cheng, Jonathan Yu. “Aspects of Character: Quantitative Evidence and Fictional People”. ETD collection for University of Nebraska-Lincoln, 2020, pp. 1–153.
- Declerck, Thierry, et al. “Multilingual Ontologies for the Representation and Processing of Folktales”. Proceedings, herausgegeben von Anca Dinu u. a., 2017, pp. 20–23.
- Declerck, Thierry, et al. “Ontology-Based Incremental Annotation of Characters in Folktales”. Proceedings of the 6th Workshop on Language Technology for Cultural Heritage, Social Sciences, and Humanities, Association for Computational Linguistics, 2012, pp. 30–34.

- Eder, Jens, et al. “Characters in Fictional Worlds. An Introduction”. Characters in Fictional Worlds. Understanding Imaginary Beings in Literature, Film, and Other Media, edited by Jens Eder et al., 2010, pp. 3–66.
- Freitas, Cláudia, and Diana Santos. “Gender Depiction in Portuguese”. Journal of Computational Literary Studies, vol. 2, no. 1, 1, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.48694/jcls.3576>.
- González-Blanco, Elena, et al. Applying Ontology Engineering to Build a Poetry Domain Ontology. 2022.
- Hinzmann, Maria, Matthias Bremm, Tinghui Duan, Julia Konstanciak, Julia Röttgermann, Moritz Steffes, Christof Schöch, and Joëlle Weis. 2024. “Patterns in modeling and querying a knowledge graph for literary history [preprint].” In Pattern Theory in Language and Communication, edited by Sabine Arndt-Lappe, Milena Belosevic, Peter Maurer, Claudine Moulin, Achim Rettinger, and Sören Stumpf. Trier: TCLC. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12080340>.
- Hoque, Md Naimul, et al. “Portrayal: Leveraging NLP and Visualization for Analyzing Fictional Characters”. Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference, ACM, 2023, pp. 74–94. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3563657.3596000>.
- Kraicer, Eve, and Andrew Piper. “Social Characters: The Hierarchy of Gender in Contemporary English-Language Fiction”. Journal of Cultural Analytics, vol. 3, no. 2, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.22148/16.032>.
- Moretti, Franco. Network Theory, Plot Analysis. 2011. <https://litlab.stanford.edu/pamphlets/>.
- Pasin, Michel, and John Bradley. “Factoid-Based Prosopography and Computer Ontologies: Towards an Integrated Approach”. Digital Scholarship in the Humanities, vol. 30, 2015, pp. 86-97, doi.org/10.1093/lhc/fqt037.
- Piper, Andrew. “What Do Characters Do? The Embodied Agency of Fictional Characters”. Journal of Computational Literary Studies, vol. 2, 1, 2023, pp. 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.48694/jcls.3589>.
- Schöch, Christof, Maria Hinzmann, Julia Röttgermann, Katharina Dietz, and Anne Klee. 2022. “Smart Modelling for Literary History.” International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing 16 (1): 78–93. <https://doi.org/10.3366/ijhac.2022.0278>.
- Trilcke, Peer. „Social Network Analysis (SNA) als Methode einer textempirischen Literaturwissenschaft“. Empirie in der Literaturwissenschaft, herausgegeben von Philip Ajouri u. a., Brill | mentis, 2013, pp. 201–47. https://doi.org/10.30965/9783957439710_012.

Zöllner-Weber, Amélie. "Formale Repräsentation und Beschreibung von literarischen Figuren".
Jahrbuch für Computerphilologie, vol. 5, 2007,
<http://computerphilologie.digital-humanities.de/jg05/zoellner-weber.html>.